

High Resolution Techno-Economic Analysis of Future Power Network Development in Southeast Asia

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Technical University Berlin

Department of Digital Transformation in Energy Systems
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Master Thesis

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Abstract

Southeast Asia, a region with a rapidly growing population and energy demand, is striving to achieve net-zero emissions by 2060 or sooner. This thesis develops a new Southeast Asia-wide electricity-only energy system model to assess the impact of an interregional grid development plan named the ASEAN Power Grid and strategies for the phase-out or phase-down of coal-fired power plants. A series of scenarios are made for comparison, spanning the years 2020 to 2050, with three network topologies and three decarbonization policy targets. These models are simplified to have 200 spatial nodes and a temporal resolution of three hours. However, due to the way the data is aggregated, they can be adjusted to achieve a higher resolution if needed.

The results indicate that expanding grid interconnections enables the region to decarbonize while maintaining annual system costs within 20% of the baseline pathway. Moreover, the phase-out or reduction of coal-fired power plants is influenced not only by their efficiency and location but also by the ASEAN Power Grid. Enhanced grid interconnections extend the operational lifespan of coal-fired power plants while still achieving comparable decarbonization goals.

Zusammenfassung

Südostasien, eine Region mit einer schnell wachsenden Bevölkerung und Energienachfrage, strebt an, bis 2060 oder früher Netto-Null-Emissionen zu erreichen. In dieser Arbeit wird ein neues südostasienweites Modell für ein rein elektrisches Energiesystem entwickelt, um die Auswirkungen eines interregionalen Netzentwicklungsplans mit der Bezeichnung ASEAN Power Grid und Strategien für den Ausstieg aus der Kohleverstromung zu bewerten. Zu Vergleichszwecken wird eine Reihe von Szenarien für die Jahre 2020 bis 2050 mit drei Netztopologien und drei politischen Dekarbonisierungszielen erstellt. Diese Modelle sind so vereinfacht, dass sie 200 räumliche Knotenpunkte und eine zeitliche Auflösung von drei Stunden haben. Wegen der Methode, mit der die Daten aggregiert werden, können sie jedoch bei Bedarf auf eine höhere Auflösung angepasst werden.

Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass der Ausbau der Netzverbindungen die Region in die Lage versetzt, die Dekarbonisierung zu erreichen und gleichzeitig die jährlichen Systemkosten innerhalb von 20% des Basisszenarios zu halten. Darüber hinaus wird der Ausstieg oder die Reduzierung von Kohlekraftwerken nicht nur durch ihre Effizienz und ihren Standort, sondern auch durch das ASEAN-Stromnetz beeinflusst. Verbesserte Netzverbindungen verlängern die Betriebsdauer von Kohlekraftwerken, während gleichzeitig vergleichbare Dekarbonisierungsziele erreicht werden.

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Abbreviations

- **1.5-S RE90:** 1.5-Scenario with 90% renewable power generation
- **ACE:** ASEAN Center for Energy
- **AEO8:** 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook
- **AIMS:** ASEAN Interconnection Masterplan Study
- **ANU:** Australian National University
- **APAEC:** ASEAN Plan of Action for Energy Cooperation
- **APG:** ASEAN Power Grid
- **ASEAN:** Association of Southeast Asian Nations
- **BAU:** Business-as-Usual
- **BECCS:** Bioenergy With Carbon Capture and Storage
- **CCS:** Carbon Capture and Storage
- **CFB:** Circulating Fluidized Bed
- **CNS:** Carbon Neutrality Scenario
- **DEC:** Deep Decarbonization Policy Target
- **EEZ:** Exclusive Economic Zone
- **ERA5:** Fifth Generation of Atmospheric Reanalysis
- **ERIA:** Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia
- **GADM:** Database of Global Administrative Areas
- **GDP:** Gross Domestic Product
- **GEM:** Global Energy Monitor
- **GHG:** Greenhouse Gas
- **HVDC:** High Voltage Direct Current
- **IEA:** International Energy Agency
- **IESR:** Institute for Essential Services Reform
- **IRENA:** International Renewable Energy Agency
- **KPI:** Key-Performance-Indicators
- **LCOE:** Levelized Cost of Electricity
- **MGA:** Modeling-to-Generate-Alternatives
- **NGO:** Non-Governmental Organization
- **OSM:** OpenStreetMap
- **PDP:** Power Development Plan
- **PV:** Photovoltaic
- **PyPSA:** Python for Power System Analysis

- **RMI:** Rocky Mountain Institute
- **SC:** Supercritical Power Plants
- **SE:** Stable Emission
- **SEA:** Southeast Asia
- **SubC:** Subcritical Power Plants
- **USC:** Ultra-Subcritical Power Plants
- **VRE:** Variable Renewable Energy

Introduction

In 2020, Southeast Asia (SEA) had a population of approximately 660 million people, with an annual GDP growth rate of 4.6%. Based on projections of a growing population to 800 million people [Asi+23] and consistent growth targets, the region's energy demand is expected to increase two to threefold—from less than 6400 TWh to more than 13000 TWh—by 2050 [@Adi+22]. The electricity demand of SEA of 1100 TWh/year can grow 2 to 6 fold in 2050. The projection decreases through energy efficiency measures [@YW22] and increase through electrification and sector coupling [@Adi+22]. SEA is therefore one of the fastest growing energy consumers in the world.

Historically, financial and economic development in the region have contributed to environmental degradation such as local pollution in the short-term and climate change in the long-term. The current SEA business model relies on foreign direct investment, which are incentivised by weak environmental regulations and inexpensive, polluting energy sources [NDX19]. This phenomena is in align with pollution haven hypothesis.

This approach is unsustainable both environmentally and economically, as the region is also highly vulnerable to extreme weather events. According to the 2000 - 2019 Global Climate Risk Index, three of the ten SEA States (Myanmar, Thailand, and the Philippines) are among the top 10 countries most affected by climate change, and half of the SEA States are in the top 20 [@Dav21].

Additionally, if the temperature increase exceeds 1.5 degrees, SEA is at risk of losing more than 35% of its GDP by 2050 due to climate change and natural hazards [@Han21]. The conclusion is clear: Failing to meet the goals set by the 2015 Paris Agreement could severely hinder the region's development.

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is an economic union of 10 states in Southeast Asia: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. All of them have committed to achieving a specific amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction around mid-century and net-zero status by 2060 or possibly earlier [@YW22]. The complete list official emissions target are shown in table 1.1.

Country	Official Emissions Target from COP 26
Brunei Darussalam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce GHG emissions by at least 10% through better supply and demand management of electricity consumption by 2035 • Reach net zero emissions by 2050
Cambodia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce GHG emissions by 42% or 64.5 Mt CO₂-eq by 2030 from the BAU level • Reach carbon neutral by 2050
Indonesia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce GHG emissions by 29% by 2030 from the BAU level • Reach net zero emissions by 2060 or sooner
Lao PDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60% GHG emission reductions compared to the Baseline Scenario by 2030, or around 62,000 kt CO₂-eq in absolute terms • Reach net zero emissions by 2050 conditionally
Malaysia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce economy-wide carbon intensity (against GDP) by 45% in 2030 compared to the 2005 level • Reach carbon neutral by 2050
Myanmar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conditional emissions reductions of 244.52 Mt CO₂-eq and unconditional reductions of 414.75 Mt CO₂-eq by 2030. • Reach carbon neutral by 2050
Philippines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce and avoid GHG emissions by 75% from BAU, of which 2.71% is unconditional and 72.29% is conditional • No carbon neutral target set during COP 26
Singapore	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieve peak emissions at 65 Mt CO₂-eq around 2030 • Reach net zero emissions by or around mid-century
Thailand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce GHG emissions by 20% by 2030 from BAU, of which 117.6 Mt CO₂-eq from the energy sector • Target carbon neutrality by 2050 and net zero emissions by 2065
Vietnam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce GHG emissions by 8% unconditional by 2030, compared to the BAU scenario • Reach net zero emissions by 2050

Tab. 1.1.: Official Emissions Target from COP 26 [@YW22]

1.1 Literature Review

The path towards climate neutrality in the SEA region is a highly discussed topic both by researchers and by policy makers. One of the means by which these stakeholder investigate and communicate the economic and technical feasibility of the energy transition is through energy system models.

1.1.1 ASEAN Energy System Models

In this subsection, we will explore energy system models that encompass the 10 ASEAN Member States, focusing on contributions from governmental organizations and NGOs.

The International Energy Agency (IEA) outlined a decarbonization pathway in their World Energy Outlook using the Global Energy and Climate Model. This model employs a partial equilibrium approach, where energy service and material demand drive the transformation and supply of primary energy, with energy prices adjusting in a feedback loop [Coz+23]. In the context of ASEAN, the model's advantage is its dynamic future pricing of primary energy. However, a drawback is that Southeast Asia (SEA) is aggregated into a single region within the Asia Pacific, leading to no spatial resolution for individual countries.

Unlike the IEA energy system model, the Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia (ERIA) provides a more detailed approach by treating each ASEAN Member State as a separate node and incorporating an interconnected power grid network. Their aim is to quantitatively describe the energy transition pathway necessary to realise ASEAN climate neutrality goals by 2050 or 2060. This results in distinct outcomes for each member state [Kim+22]. Both the ERIA and IEA models highlight the importance of scaling up renewable energy, increasing electrification, and moving away from coal-fired power plants. However, the ERIA analysis places greater emphasis on the role of fossil fuels with carbon capture, as well as hydrogen and ammonia [WA23].

Also in 2022, the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), in collaboration with the ASEAN Center of Energy (ACE), published the Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN. Their goal is to demonstrate how the region can increase its renewable energy share from 19% in 2018 to 65% by 2050, while simultaneously reducing energy-related carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by 75% compared to current policy projections. This report incorporates IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlooks for Malaysia and Indonesia, providing higher spatial resolution. Indonesia is generally divided by its provinces, while Malaysia is divided into the Malay Peninsula, Sabah, and Sarawak. This results in a detailed analysis of electricity trade between subregions [Adi+22].

In the literature review of ASEAN energy system models, a notable trend is that higher spatial resolution increases the significance of interregional grid integration. A common grid development plan both ERIA and IRENA include in their model is the ASEAN Power Grid.

1.1.2 ASEAN Power Grid (APG)

The ASEAN Power Grid is a continuous initiative designed to link the power grids of ASEAN Member States. The groundwork for promoting energy trade within ASEAN started with the 1986 Agreement on ASEAN Energy Cooperation. The concept of an ASEAN Power Grid was first officially introduced in the 1999-2004 ASEAN Plan of Action for Energy Cooperation (APAEC), which also included the initial ASEAN Interconnection Masterplan Study (AIMS I) [ACA24].

The ASEAN Interconnection Masterplan Study (AIMS) was initiated by the ASEAN Ministers on Energy Meeting to assess the feasibility of multilateral electricity trading within the ASEAN region. Its objective is to develop a comprehensive master plan for the ASEAN Power Grid and evaluate its techno-economic feasibility as a means to support the use of variable renewable energy (VRE). The study has progressed through AIMS I, AIMS II, and AIMS III, each phase building upon and updating the original concept [ACA24].

The modeling approach consists of two stages. The first stage involves planning the ASEAN Power Grid capacity expansion using PLEXOS. In this model, each country is simplified into a single node, except for Indonesia (Java, Sumatra, and Kalimantan) and Malaysia (Peninsular, Sabah, and Sarawak). Consequently, the model assumes no internal transmission constraints within each country. To address this limitation, a second modeling approach is employed, involving grid analysis with Siemens PSS/E software. This approach utilizes the load and generation data from the first stage to assess the impact on the grid, considering each country's future transmission plans [ACA24].

Before the first APAEC of 1999-2004, electricity trade agreements were only established bilaterally. Following this period, there was a concerted effort to establish, facilitate, and expedite the analyses produced by the AIMS. A landmark achievement of these efforts is the multilateral power trade agreements such as the Laos-Thailand-Malaysia Power Interconnection Project of 2019, which expanded to include Singapore as well in 2022 [AJ20].

Interconnection in Southeast Asia can extend beyond the regions proposed by AIMS. For instance, IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN suggests interconnections

between existing countries not covered by AIMS such as direct connections between Thailand and Vietnam, as well as between islands in Indonesia, namely Sulawesi and Nusa-Tenggara [@Adi+22].

ERIA includes grid interconnections among countries, with a current capacity of 5.7 GW as of 2021, and a future limit of 55 GW. However, ERIA does not provide detailed explanations of the interconnection layout, stating only that it is based on the planned capacity and feedback from each country [@Kim+22].

A key takeaway from AIMS III which also aligns with IRENA's results is that enhancing regional interconnections boosts VRE utilization. Conversely, scenarios with ambitious VRE use require greater interconnection capacity compared to scenarios that assumes the dispatch of new coal-fired power plants capacity [ACA24].

1.1.3 ASEAN Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down Strategy

Fig. 1.1.: Coal-fired power plants in Southeast Asia

To achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 or 2060, the region must not only halt the permitting of new coal-fired power plants but also retire existing ones ahead of their expected lifespans. This is because ASEAN holds the youngest coal-fired power plants in the world [@Coz21] with 53% of its capacity being less than a decade old [@PS24]. If unchanged, there will still be at least 96 GW of coal-fired power plants in 2050, as shown in Figure 1.1. To promote the phase-out of coal-fired power plants, several initiative have been establish which includes but not limited to:

- Energy Transition Mechanism from the Asian Development Bank uses concessional and commercial capital to phase-out individual fossil fuel power plants.
- Just Energy Transition Partnership provides financial support to countries in return for commitments to accelerate their energy transition.
- The Managed Phaseout Program by the Glasgow Financial Alliance for Net Zero (GFANZ) provides a framework for financial institutions to phase-out coal power plants [ATB24]

Generally, this initiatives aims to buy out coal-fired power plants and decommission them earlier than their technical and commercial lifetimes. Despite its controversy for not adhering to the polluter pays principle [Sau24], the key question for this scheme or any phase-out policy remains: which coal-fired power plants should be shut down first, and when?

To address this question, many NGOs utilize tools such as techno-economic metrics and cost-benefit analysis to evaluate each coal-fired power plant. In response to the Just Energy Transition Partnership, the Institute for Essential Services Reform (IESR) assesses potential coal-fired power plants for decommissioning through both top-down national net-zero transition pathways and bottom-up plant-level evaluations [Cui+22]. On the other hand, TransitionZero offers a Coal Asset Transition Tool that includes the costs of canceling Power Purchase Agreements, replacing lost capacity with clean alternatives, and other economic and social considerations [Gra22]. A joint report by the Rocky Mountain Institute (RMI), Sierra Club, and Carbon Tracker uses the difference between long-run marginal cost and the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) of renewable energy sources and storage to analyze the competitiveness of coal-fired power plants. [Bod+20].

The ASEAN Center of Energy (ACE) have provided criticism to the methodologies of coal-phaseout analysis which can be summarized as the following:

- The analysis places too much emphasis on LCOE, overlooking the crucial role of dispatchable capacity in lowering the overall cost of the energy system.
- The analysis overlooked the external cost associated with variable renewable energy, including cost for grid capacity expansion and renewable energy curtailment, among others.

ACE advocates for a coal phase-down, which emphasize decreasing reliance on coal-fired power plants instead of a complete phase-out. They stress that these plants should be decommissioned at the appropriate time, ensuring that the necessary infrastructure and renewable energy sources are in place [PS24].

1.2 Research Gap and Question

1.2.1 Research Gap

Based on the previous discussion, although there are numerous studies on the future energy systems of the region, certain aspects of their analyses could be further refined:

- Many studies focus on clusters of multiple countries (EIA) or use a single node per country (ERIA), province, or state (AIMS, IRENA). This approach has led to the energy system planning model underestimating the regional characteristics of renewable energy, as well as the costs and requirements for internal grid capacity expansion.
- Analyses of coal phase-out often overlook the overall system costs associated with variable renewable energy, particularly regarding grid capacity requirements, curtailments, and other related factors (IESR, TransitionZero, RMI, Sierra Club, and Carbon Tracker).

All these models and analyses can benefit from an energy system model that simulates the grid with higher resolution. One such model is PyPSA-Earth, an open-source global energy system model that offers a powerful tool for modeling the world's energy system with high spatial and temporal resolution [Par+23]. By integrating existing open-source energy data compiled by PyPSA-Earth with some fine-tuning, we can optimize and analyse both the ASEAN Power Grid and the coal phase-out/phase-down strategy.

As of 2024, there is no publicly accessible model of the SEA region using PyPSA-Earth. Therefore, we define PyPSA-SEA as a PyPSA-Earth model tailored specifically for the Southeast Asia region. This model encompasses the ASEAN member states: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam, simulating their energy supply, demand, exports, and imports in relation to each other.

1.2.2 Research Question

The PyPSA-SEA model has the potential to fill this research gap. The primary research questions are: "What are the economic impacts of new interregional grid interconnections and of the phase-out or phase-down of coal in the energy transition of Southeast Asia, and how are these two factors interrelated?"

In the context of the ASEAN Power Grid, both AIMS and IRENA have proposed new interregional interconnections to currently unconnected regions. The detailed research questions regarding this topic are:

- 1a) What are the cost-optimal energy system development pathways with and without these interconnections proposed by AIMS and IRENA?
- 1b) How do these pathways differ in terms of the distribution of renewable and grid infrastructure in the region?
- 1c) What are the benefits and drawbacks for countries and subregions before and after their grids are interconnected?

In the context of the coal phase-out/phase-down strategy, organizations such as IESR, TransitionZero, RMI, Sierra Club, and Carbon Tracker have developed tools to prioritize which coal-fired power plants should be decommissioned first. The detailed research questions regarding this topic are:

- 2a) What are the cost-optimal energy system development pathways under different decarbonization policy targets?
- 2b) How do these pathways impact the prioritization and scheduling for the decommissioning of coal-fired power plants?

Since the utilization of interregional interconnections is influenced by decarbonization pathways, while the feasibility of phasing out or reducing coal usage depends on the availability of renewable energy, there is an interconnection between the two topics. This raises a new research question not yet addressed in existing literature:

- 3) How does the interregional grid interconnections interrelate with the prioritization and scheduling for the decommissioning of coal-fired power plants?

To address this questions, the thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 2 covers the PyPSA-SEA dataset which includes datasets from PyPSA-Earth and additional data to better model the SEA region. **Chapter 3** outlines the thesis methodologies which consist of the base configuration, variations of the models, and the primary focus of the analysis. **Chapter 4** presents the results of the analysis, providing key insights of an ASEAN Power Grid and Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down Strategies. **Chapter 5** Discuss the validity of the model through historical comparison, comparison of well known literature and sensitivity analysis of certain parameters. **Chapter 6** explores the implications of these results, comparing and contrasting them with the literature reviewed in the introduction.

The PyPSA-SEA Dataset

In this chapter, we highlight and detail all the data used for the PyPSA-SEA model. This includes a combination of open-source data provided within the PyPSA-Earth program and additional data necessary for the context of this thesis.

2.1 Base Data from PyPSA-Earth

PyPSA (Python for Power System Analysis) is an open-sourced framework for simulating and optimizing energy systems. It is a Python package that includes pre-compiled equations, algorithms, and interfaces to conduct and analyze energy system models. Users can incorporate conventional generators, variable renewable energy sources, storage units, energy lines, and links. The program then optimizes the capacity and usage of each component to cost-effectively meet the energy demand [BHS17].

The advantage of PyPSA lies in its ability to create high temporal and spatial resolution models. However, this capability is highly dependent on the temporal and spatial resolutions of the underlying data. PyPSA does not provide data for its models. Users need to input existing energy infrastructure, weather, and other environmental, technological, and economic data. This can be done on a case-by-case basis or by utilizing the open-source data compiled by PyPSA-Earth.

2.1.1 Environmental Data

PyPSA-Earth uses the Database of Global Administrative Areas (GADM) [GAD22] and the Economic Exclusive Zones (EEZ) to define the shape of countries, land area and sea area respectively. The maps and geographic data from GADM and EEZ are intended solely for modeling purposes. They do not imply any political stance or endorsement of any territorial claims.

Additionally, PyPSA-Earth uses ERA5 reanalysis data for weather-related information. ERA5 is the fifth generation of atmospheric reanalysis produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts. It covers the global climate from 1950 onwards [Her+20]. The key advantage of ERA5 reanalysis is its hourly temporal resolution and $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ spatial resolution [Hof+21].

Global historical weather data, such as wind speed and solar influxes, are converted into weather-dependent energy system data using the Python package Atlite. A typical workflow of Atlite in PyPSA-Earth consists of these steps:

1. **Creating a cutout:** Select the spatio-temporal boundaries [Hof+21]. The base model of PyPSA-SEA defines the spatial boundaries with longitudes ranging from 90° to 141.9° and latitudes from -15° to 30°. The model uses the year 2018 as the reference snapshot year, with additional years included for sensitivity analysis.
2. **Preparing the cutout:** Gather environmental and weather data from various open datasets [Hof+21]. ERA5 reanalysis are used for weather related data [Her+20] and the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans for the terrain heights [@GEB24]. Although SARAH-2 satellite data are also available, it was not used in this thesis because it does not include the SEA region [@AHM21].
3. **Defining land-use restrictions:** Limit the deployment of renewable infrastructure [Hof+21]. The eligible areas are constrained by technological, environmental, and social factors. The land availability for each renewable technology is determined using the global land cover provided by the Copernicus project [@Cop20]. No modifications have been made for PyPSA-SEA from PyPSA-Earth.
4. **Converting the cutout:** Atlite processes this input to calculate the power generation potential and time series for each renewable energy technologies per region [Hof+21]. In the version PyPSA-Earth used in this thesis, Atlite is used to estimate the renewable potential of solar energy (both photovoltaic and concentrated solar power), wind energy (both onshore and offshore), and hydro-power [Par+23].

2.1.2 Technological Data

PyPSA-Earth uses the grid infrastructure data extracted from OpenStreetMaps as the foundational dataset for existing power grid topology [@Ope24]. The grid topology is extracted and simplified from transmission lines and substations, converting them into lines and nodes compatible with PyPSA [Par+23]. Numerous modifications have been made to the power grid topology of PyPSA-SEA, which are detailed in the additional data in Section 2.2.

The technology data for PyPSA-Earth are derived from the repository maintained by the Photovoltaic Solar Energy group at the Department of Engineering at Aarhus University and the Department of Digital Transformation in Energy Systems at the Technische Universität Berlin [@UB24]. Modification have been made for coal technologies for PyPSA-SEA, which are detailed in the augmented data section.

PyPSA-Earth uses the Python packages `powerplantmatching` to compile and standardize power plants from various power plant databases, primarily from the Global Energy Monitor (GEM) [Mon24] but also from the World Resources Institute [Ins24] and the Global Energy Observatory [Obs18]. This data encompasses both conventional and renewable power plants, with the renewable data further enhanced using IRENA's national renewable energy capacity statistics [IRE24].

2.1.3 Economic Data

Finding data on hourly electricity demand for many countries can be challenging, including in the SEA region. Only Singapore, Thailand, and the Philippines have open data, while the remaining seven ASEAN countries do not provide accessible data. To address this, PyPSA-Earth integrates various data sources with differing spatial and temporal resolutions, aiming to achieve the highest possible resolution across all dimensions.

The national-level hourly temporal resolution in PyPSA-Earth is synthetically generated using a machine learning approach [Mat+21]. The total electricity demand of PyPSA-Earth for a given year is extrapolated based on the shared socioeconomic pathway corresponding to a 2-2.6°C temperature increase. PyPSA-SEA utilizes only the demand curve, while the annual electricity demand is sourced from a different dataset, which is further detailed in the augmented data section.

The total electricity demand of each country is distributed using a rasterized grid based on population data from WorldPop [Wor24] and GDP data from DRYAD [KTG18], according to the following equation:

$$factors = \left(0.6 \cdot \frac{GDP_{region}}{GDP_{total}} + 0.4 \cdot \frac{Population_{region}}{Population_{total}} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

The relative factors of 0.6 and 0.4 were derived from a linear regression analysis of load data from EU countries.

2.2 Additional Data for South-East Asia

The OpenStreetMaps grid topology offers information exclusively on existing transmission lines. Given that the PyPSA-SEA model is designed to simulate scenarios up to 2050, it has to incorporate transmission lines currently under construction or under consideration by ASEAN states government as well. To achieve this, we refer to the map of national power development plans, as summarized in Table 2.1. Using the location

names provided in these plans, we identify the substation on Google Maps and use its coordinates as the basis for the modified network topology. If the substation isn't found at that location, alternative power infrastructure is used as a surrogate.

Fig. 2.1.: The SEA network topology and its sources: OpenStreetMaps and National Power Development Plans form the internal network. AIMS and IRENA interregional network form the ASEAN Power Grid

The PyPSA-SEA model integrates grid networks for all countries and subregions by combining national power development plans with precompiled OpenStreetMap data. This internal integration allows each country and subregion to be clustered into a single node. However, Nusa-Tenggara and Papua are exceptions, as Indonesia's national power development plans do not propose their integration.

To model future interregional connections, we incorporate the ASEAN power grid connection proposed in AIMS. We also include the ASEAN Power Grid model from IRENA's ASEAN Renewable Energy Outlook. Since few national government sources specify the exact locations of interregional connections, we make assumptions about these connections using a similar method as for the internal grid networks. The resulting network topology are shown in Figure 2.1.

Fig. 2.2.: PyPSA-SEA electricity demand assumption with detailed data for the year 2050

Rather than utilizing the precompiled national annual electricity demand from PyPSA-Earth, PyPSA-SEA employs data from EMBER for the 2020 electricity demand of the 10 ASEAN Member States [@EMB24]. For the year 2050, we have selected IRENA’s 1.5-Scenario, which projects an annual electricity demand of 6403 TWh with 90% renewable energy. The annual demands for the years between 2020 and 2050 are interpolated using a second-degree polynomial. The results are shown in Figure 2.2.

Using IRENA’s annual electricity demand assumptions does not necessarily mean that the electricity sector itself is fully decarbonized. It means that it accounts for the additional electricity demand arising from the decarbonization and electrification of other sectors, such as industry and transport, required to meet the 1.5-degree climate target of these sectors.

Finally, for a detailed decommissioning analysis, we classify coal-fired power plants not only by their fuel sources—hard coal and lignite—but also by their combustion technologies: subcritical (SubC), supercritical (SC), ultra-supercritical (USC), and circulating fluidized bed (CFB) types, with respective combustion efficiencies of 38%, 42%, 45%, and 38% [@12]. These differences influence both the marginal price and the carbon emissions per unit of electricity generated.

To determine which combustion technologies are used by coal-fired power plants, we first revisit the source data used to compile power plants in the region, specifically the Python package `powerplantmatching`. We search and match the combustion technology using three sources: the Global Energy Monitor’s Global Coal Plant Tracker [Mon24], the World Resource Institute’s Global Power Plant Database [Ins24], and the Global Energy Observatory Power Plants [Obs18]. The former and the latter provide the most and second most detailed information on combustion technologies, respectively, while the World Resource Institute’s Global Power Plant Database offers the least information. After filtering the power plants based on their combustion technology, any remaining plants with unclear information are investigated individually. If unresolved, they are classified as unknown.

For coal-fired power plants with unspecified combustion technologies, we apply an efficiency of 33% as indicated in the original technology cost data. Due to their limited number, lignite-based coal-fired power plants are not classified by combustion technology. Other parameters from the technology cost data, such as the investment per capacity added, remain unchanged.

Figure 1.1 in Chapter 1.1 illustrates the outcome of this effort. On an annual average, coal-fired power plants using subcritical combustion technology make up 63.9% of the fleet’s capacity. Supercritical and ultra-supercritical technologies account for 17.4% and 3.4%, respectively, while lignite and circulating fluidized bed contribute 6.1% and 5.2%, respectively.

Country	Sources	Citation
Cambodia	Electricite Du Cambodge 2017	[@Éle18]
Indonesia	Perusahaan Listrik Negara 2020	[@Dir21]
Lao PDR	Electricite du Laos (from ERIA 2021)	[KU21]
Malaysia		
- Sabah	Energy Commission of Sabah 2023	[@Ene23]
- Sarawak	Sarawak Energy	[@Sar]
Myanmar	Ministry of Electric Power 2019	[@Mya19]
Philippines	National Grid Corporation of the Philippines 2020	[@Nat20]
Singapore	Open source from GENI	[@Glo]

Tab. 2.1.: Sources of additional data of National Power Development Plan

Methodologies

This section details the methodologies used in this thesis to address the research questions outlined in the subsection 1.2.2.

For this thesis we create a “cost-optimal energy system” named PyPSA-SEA, a tailored version of PyPSA-Earth designed specifically for the Southeast Asia region. Consequently, the configuration of this model differs from the base configuration of PyPSA-Earth, with these differences detailed in section 3.1.

Models utilizing the PyPSA framework impose spatial and temporal boundaries to manage computational complexities. Typically, these models are configured to run over a one-year period. However, simulating “pathways” necessitates a time frame longer than a single year. Therefore, a series of models from the year 2020 to 2050 with 5 year steps is created. The differences between these models across different years are detailed in section 3.2.

To answer research questions 1a), 1b), 1c) and 3) we compare the current interconnections and those proposed by AIMS and IRENA. To facilitate this comparison, three categories of models of network configurations were created. The differences in these configurations are detailed in section 3.3.

To answer research questions 2a), 2b) and 3) we compare different decarbonization policy targets and see its impact on the decommissioning of coal-fired powerplants. To have a clear point of comparison, this thesis has defined three decarbonization policy targets, namely a policy with no emission limits, a policy maintaining relatively stable annual emissions, and a policy aiming for a 90% reduction in annual emissions by mid-century. Further details on these targets are in section 3.4.

Based on the information provided, we illustrate the range of models utilized in this thesis in Figure 3.1. With seven temporal scopes, three network topologies, and three decarbonization policy targets, the thesis employs at least 63 PyPSA models. While these models are related, they operate independently, meaning the results of one model do not affect the others. This is one out of many limitations of the models, which are detailed further in section 3.5.

Fig. 3.1.: PyPSA-SEA array of models and its three dimensions.

3.1 Base Model Configuration

Due to the fragmented geography of Malaysia and Indonesia, their grid networks are not internally integrated. When running the model on the base PyPSA-Earth configuration, automatically generated connections are created, which must be avoided for this analysis. To achieve this, Malaysia is divided into the Malay Peninsula, Sabah, and Sarawak, while Indonesia is split into Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and Papua.

Splitting these countries into subregions allows the subregional network to be internally intergrated while still being separated from other networks in the same country. From the perspective of PyPSA-SEA, these subregions are no different from countries and are modeled as such, as shown in Figure 3.2. Their electricity demand, load curve, and load distribution however remain consistent with before the separation.

Each model’s networks are internally integrated within countries and subregions. This integration is based on the data referenced in Chapter 2.2. All lines and links added from this data initially have no capacity, allowing the optimizer to decide their utilization.

Fig. 3.2.: Countries and subregions with their respective original countries indicated as (I) for Indonesia and (M) for Malaysia

Each model's networks are clustered into 200 buses. These buses are initially allocated to each country and subregion according to the proportion of their land areas, except for Brunei and Singapore, which are city-states, and Maluku and Papua, due to their isolated nature. Within each country and subregion, the buses are then distributed based on load.

The base weather and load year for the model networks is 2018. To avoid overfitting the model to this year, sensitivity analyses are performed using the years 2011 and 2013, selected because the weather and load curve data for 2011 and 2013 are available in the default PyPSA-Earth databundle.

In all models, each node has the option to dispatch Combined Cycle Gas Turbines to meet the network's electricity demand. It is the sole dispatchable conventional power plant. New coal-fired power plants cannot be constructed in this model, except for those already approved, which will continue to be dispatched in future years.

All models operate under a greenfield overnight approach, which means they consider existing and expandable infrastructure to meet the electricity demand. However, models for future years are not influenced by those from previous years. In other words, this model does not incorporate any foresight.

3.2 Temporal Scope Configuration

Each model represents a specific year ranging from 2020 to 2050 in five-year increments. The primary differences between these years are the total annual load demand and technology costs.

The annual load demand for each year is derived by interpolating the actual electricity demand of 2020 with the projected annual electricity demand for 2050 according to IRENA's 1.5-Scenario.

The technology cost datasets referenced in Chapter 2.1.2 change annually, influencing the economic viability of certain technologies. For instance, the investment costs for renewable technologies are projected to decrease over time. Additionally, since all models assume the initial renewable capacity of 2020 and capacity expansion from model runs in previous years are neglected, this creates distortions in the total system cost as projections extend into the future. To address these distortions, adjustments are made to the total system cost by adding the capital cost from the initial year to the capital cost of the newly added capacities. These adjustments are made iteratively as the years progress, while the marginal cost component of the total system cost remains unaffected. This is done during the analysis phase post optimization.

3.3 Network Topology Configuration

The thesis has defined three categories of network:

- **Existing Network:** Only existing interregional interconnections are included.
- **AIMS Network:** All of the interconnections that are under construction or proposed by AIMS are included in addition to the existing interregional interconnections.
- **IRENA Network:** All of the interconnections modeled in IRENA's ASEAN Renewable Outlook are included in addition to the existing, constructed and proposed interconnections from AIMS.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the network of interconnections among countries and subregions. Currently, these connections exist solely within mainland Southeast Asia. The AIMS proposal aims to link all ASEAN member states, whereas the IRENA models offer the most comprehensive coverage. Regardless of the simulation year, all interconnections

either proposed by AIMS or IRENA are included with initial transmission capacity based on its determined voltages, allowing the optimizer to decide their utilization.

Fig. 3.3.: Existing and proposed interregional interconnection schematics

3.4 Decarbonization Policy Targets Configuration

The thesis has defined three categories of decarbonization policy targets:

- **Business As Usual:** Models are unconstrained by any emission limits
- **Stable Emission:** The total annual emission of the year 2050 is equal to the year 2020
- **Deep Decarbonization:** The total annual emission of the year 2050 is equal to 10% of the year 2020

The trendlines of the total annual emission limits for the Stable Emission $E_{stable}(y)$ and Deep Decarbonization policy $E_{dec}(y)$ between the year 2020 and 2050 are determined using this function:

$$E_{stable}(y) = E_{ave}(y) \cdot r(y) \tag{3.1}$$

$$E_{dec}(y) = E_{ave}(y) \cdot r(y) \cdot t(y) \tag{3.2}$$

$$r(y) = 1 \cdot \left(\frac{2050 - y}{2050 - 2020} \right) + \frac{E_{ave}(2020)}{E_{ave}(2050)} \cdot \left(\frac{y - 2020}{2050 - 2020} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

$$t(y) = 1 \cdot \left(\frac{2050 - y}{2050 - 2020} \right) + 0.1 \cdot \left(\frac{y - 2020}{2050 - 2020} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

$E_{ave}(y)$ represents the average model results from all network configurations using the No Limits policy for that year. $r(y)$ is a linear interpolation of emissions between 2020 and 2050, designed to counteract increasing emissions, ensuring that the annual emissions in 2020 are equal to those in 2050. Conversely, $t(y)$ is a linear interpolation aimed at achieving a 90% reduction in emissions by 2050 compared to 2020.

Emissions are produced by both existing and newly dispatched conventional power plants. The emission rate of powerplants are calculated using this formula:

$$E_{gen} = \sum_t^y D_{gen,t} \cdot \frac{EFCO2_{c(gen)}}{\eta_{c(gen)}} \quad (3.5)$$

Formula 3.5 indicates that the annual emission rate for each power plant E_{gen} is determined by the amount of electricity it produces $\sum_t^y D_{gen,t}$, multiplied by the emission factor $EFCO2_{c(gen)}$ and divided by the efficiency of electricity generated per unit of fuel consumed $\eta_{c(gen)}$. The emission factor and efficiency are both dependent on the type of energy carrier $c(gen)$ used. When annual emission constraints are applied, the model will prioritize power plants with lower emissions per unit of electricity generated until the emission reduction targets are met.

The emission factor depends entirely on its fuel types. Lignite, coal and gas has an emission factor of 0.41, 0.34 and 0.2 tonnes/MWh respectively. The efficiency on the other hand depends on the technology the power plants are using. This is why Combined Cycle Gas Turbines produce less emission compared to Open Cycle Gas Turbines despite of both of them using the same fuel. The standard version of PyPSA-Earth only distinguishes coal-fired power plants by its fuel and not its technology [UB24]. Using the modification mentioned in Chapter 2.2 all power plants with "coal" as its carrier are further differentiated into the following technology:

- **Subcritical:** Conventional pulverised coal combustion technology. 38% Efficiency
- **Supercritical:** Steam generation at pressure above waters critical point. 42% Efficiency
- **Ultra-Supercritical:** Steam generation with temperature higher than Supercritical. 45% Efficiency

- **Circulating Fluidized Bed:** Coal combustion under lower temperature. 38% Efficiency
- **Unknown:** Unknown technology. Resort to the PyPSA-Earth default technology efficiency of 33% [@12]

There are two additional information regarding coal-fired power plants in all the models. First, all captive coal-fired power plants are excluded because they do not participate in regional electricity markets. Second, the operational lifetime of coal-fired power plants is limited to 30 years, rather than their technical lifespan of 40 years. This adjustment aligns with the ACE report, which is endorsed by both ASEAN energy ministries and the ASEAN Forum on Coal [@PS24].

3.5 Model Limitations

Although the design of PyPSA-SEA is thorough and effective in addressing the stated research questions, the model has several limitations that are managed through approximations and assumptions. Furthermore, there are many components of an energy system in Southeast Asia that are not included but are worth improving on future iterations. Here is an incomplete list of the model limitations:

3.5.1 Approximations

- **Impacts on other sector on the electricity demand:** To ensure comparability, all scenarios assume the same electricity demand growth, irrespective of their decarbonization policy targets. The IRENA 1.5°C Scenario incorporates decarbonization and electrification within the industry, transport, and building sectors. The decarbonization policy targets does not impact the extent of decarbonization of these sectors.
- **Non sequential yearly dispatch of extendable technologies:** The version of PyPSA-Earth used in this thesis does not yet include a planning horizon, and all models are independent of the results from the corresponding previous year. As a result, the model may have less generator or line capacity compared to the previous year, despite remaining within the technology's lifetime.
- **Distribution of internal electricity demand:** The allocation of electricity demand within countries is determined using a rasterized grid based on population and GDP data, as outlined in Chapter 2.1.3. Because population distribution shifts with increasing urbanization rates and the GDP data only extends to 2015, this approach underestimates the growing concentration of electricity demand in cities.

- **Coal-fired Power Plants Dispatch Flexibility:** Given that coal-fired power plants are central to the decommissioning analysis, it's crucial to have them operate as baseload without exceeding their technical dispatch flexibility. To ensure this, we can enable the unit commitment function for generators in PyPSA. However, with up to 149 coal-fired power plants, the computational time to solve a single model exceeds three hours, and the final results remain undetermined. As a result, the model does not use unit commitment.
- **Transmission Data Completeness:** The modified network topology encompasses a limited number of analyzed countries as shown in Table 2.1. The included lines specify only their voltage values, not their capacities or those of the HVDC links. This lack of detail stems from the uncertainty about the number of cables per transmission line. Consequently, the model itself must determine the optimal use of these lines based on their capacity.
- **Voronoi-based Offshore Partition:** The model relies on the EEZ for partitioning the offshore region. To divide a country into subregions, the offshore area must also be further partitioned. Since the center point for the Voronoi diagram starts at the second GADM level, this results in exaggerated offshore regions for small islands and smaller offshore regions for large islands, impacting the estimation of offshore wind potential.

3.5.2 Assumptions

- **Liberalized Electricity Trading System:** The model assumes that there are no limits on the amount of electricity a country or subregion can trade in order to achieve the optimal marginal price for the region.
- **Collective budget and emission targets:** The model presumes that all countries pool their carbon budgets and allocate them according to the needs and limitations of each country's and subregion's renewable potential.

3.5.3 Incompleteness

- **Special Economic Zones and Captive Power Plants:** One factor in the ASEAN energy system is the role of Special Economic Zones in concentrating industrial demand within localized areas. To ensure industries have access to the cheapest and most consistent electricity, they typically use captive power plants. This model excludes the impact of Special Economic Zones and captive power plants because the model is not sector coupled.
- **ASEAN Gas Pipeline:** The ASEAN Gas Pipeline is a transnational project developed alongside the ASEAN Power Grid. With the growing reliance on flexible dispatchable power plants during the energy transition, the availability of natural

gas and its potential use as a hydrogen network is a noteworthy topic. However, this model excludes these considerations.

- **Regional Dependent Storage Technologies:** The mountainous terrain and numerous water bodies in Southeast Asia provide significant potential for pumped hydro in the region's energy storage capacities. The Global Greenfield Pumped Hydro Energy Storage Atlas, developed by the Australia National University (ANU), is already suitable for this purpose [24]. The main challenge lies in implementing it within PyPSA-Earth, while considering the land eligibility requirements already factored into other renewable technologies.
- **Dispatchable renewable technologies:** Bioenergy and Geothermal are both dispatchable renewable technologies that are included in IRENA's ASEAN Renewable Outlook [Adi+22] and ASEAN Energy Outlook 8 [SY24]. The version of PyPSA-Earth used in this thesis does not yet include these option as being dispatchable.
- **New Energy Technologies:** ACE has analyzed nuclear and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) as potential alternative energy sources to replace coal [PS24]. These technologies from a modeling perspective face technical constraints, such as the availability of underground caverns, and social constraints in regards to the construction of nuclear power plants. Due to these uncertainties, they are not included in the analysis.

3.6 Model Development Potential

PyPSA and PyPSA-Earth are undergoing rapid development for modeling energy transitions. The model code for this thesis was forked from PyPSA-Earth version 0.3.0. By the time of submission, PyPSA-Earth had advanced to version 0.4.1, incorporating features such as sector coupling and myopic foresight. For this thesis to be replicated in the current version of PyPSA-Earth, two features needs to be intergrated upstream:

- **Subregions:** The options to divide countries into multiple independent subregions is not yet available in the upstream version of PyPSA-Earth. This limitation arises because the current implementation of this feature introduces misalignment between national datasets and the subregional model. A more effective approach would involve incorporating this feature after data input but before any subsequent modifications to the model.
- **Coal Technologies:** The current version of the Python Powerplantmatching package does not include the ability to differentiate coal-fired power plants by their combustion technologies. Much of the data on combustion technologies is available through the Global Energy Monitor, though additional sources may require further

investigation. It is also crucial to consider the accuracy of power plant status data, as some databases may continue to list decommissioned or canceled power plants.

This outlines the minimum requirements for replicating this thesis using the upstream version of PyPSA-Earth. The documentation for the code and results referenced in this thesis is organized into three sections:

- **PyPSA-SEA:** A modified version (fork) of PyPSA-Earth with the necessary features to replicate the thesis. Available on GitHub [vir24b].
- **PyPSA-SEA-Toolbox:** A GitHub repository containing tools for preparing and analyzing PyPSA-SEA. Available on GitHub [vir24a].
- **PyPSA-SEA-Results:** A Zenodo repository hosting 63 PyPSA-SEA results. Available on Zenodo

Results

This section presents the optimization results of the 63 PyPSA models, following the configurations outlined in the methodology. We begin by establishing a baseline pathway, optimizing the systems for the lowest cost without imposing any emission constraints, utilizing only existing interconnections. Next, we explore potential decarbonization pathways and compare them to the baseline. Then, we come to the primary focus of this chapter, namely the detailed spatial and temporal analysis of the ASEAN power grid and the coal phase-out/phase-down strategies.

4.1 Baseline Pathway

The baseline pathway represents a series of model outcomes that achieve the lowest cost each year, adhering to the Business as Usual decarbonization policy (BAU) targets and utilizing only the existing network topology. As electricity demand increases across the region, both renewable and gas-fired power plants are dispatched at demand hotspots. Figure 4.1 shows the spatial distribution of power plant capacities in the year 2050.

Additionally, Figure 4.2 provides a pathway overview of the entire energy system. On the top left it illustrates the annual increase in power plant capacities and on the top right the corresponding energy production to meet electricity demand. As renewable energy sources, particularly solar PV, become the largest capacity and energy source in the region, there is also a growing demand for gas-fired power plants.

The bottom Figure 4.2 illustrates the causes of this through a time series of one week. To minimize costs, the model invests in solar PV and batteries up to a certain point and the remaining demand is supplied by gas-fired power plants at night, and baseload power throughout the day.

When focusing on coal-fired power plants, solar PV did not decrease the electricity generated from coal. The average capacity factor for all coal power plants ranges from 68% to nearly 100% depending on the technology. This indicates that existing coal capacities will not be phased out independently unless external emission-constraining measures are implemented.

Fig. 4.1.: PyPSA-SEA with 2050 electricity demand under Business as Usual decarbonization policy targets and existing network topology

In the absence of emission-constraining measures, all combustion-based power plants can freely dispatch their energy, resulting in a doubling of annual carbon emissions over the decades, as shown in the Figure 4.2 on the center left. However, with new coal-fired power plant construction limited to those already planned and the share of renewable energy increasing, the emission intensity of the overall system decreases from 453 to 167 gCO₂ per kWh.

The estimated annualized system cost for the baseline pathway in 2050 is projected to be €323 billion per year. This growth in renewable energy is driven by technological advancements and a reduction in costs for solar PV by 34% and batteries by 72% compared to 2020 levels. Despite the sixfold increase in electricity demand compared to 2020, the annualized system cost only triples over this period, resulting in a decrease in electricity cost from 84 to 50 €/MWh.

Fig. 4.2.: PyPSA-SEA under BAU **Top Left:** Capacity development **Top Right:** Electricity development **Center Left:** Annual emission source **Center Right:** Annual system cost **Bottom:** Time series of the year 2050 between 01.05 and 07.05

Even without additional interregional interconnections and emission constraints, the renewable share in the electricity system already surpasses 60% by 2050. However,

technological advancements alone are insufficient to achieve further decarbonization, which we will discuss next.

4.2 Decarbonization Pathways

There are two main approaches that have the potential to achieve further decarbonization: extending the interconnections and hence its network topologies and setting more ambitious decarbonization policy targets.

4.2.1 Network Topology

Expanding the network topologies involves incorporating the interconnections suggested by AIMS or modeled by IRENA. The AIMS network topology links Myanmar, Indonesia, Malaysia, and the Philippines to mainland Southeast Asian countries. In contrast, IRENA's network topology extends further, connecting additional countries and islands in eastern Indonesia, as previously shown in the methodology Figure 3.3. When the option to extend interconnections between previously unconnected regions is chosen, the improvements are minimal as seen by comparing Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.1. Both the existing network models and those from IRENA show only slight differences in capacity and energy development pathways. The AIMS network map can be found in Appendix Figure A.1

By implementing the network topologies proposed by AIMS and IRENA, the share of renewable energy rises from 60% to 64% and 66% under BAU policy targets, respectively. This results in a reduction of total emissions by 7% for AIMS's topology and 11% for IRENA's by the year 2050. Expanding the sources of renewable energy decreases the reliance on fossil fuels, particularly gas-fired power plants, which generate 343 TWh less electricity in IRENA's network topology.

Upon implementing the AIMS network topology, the interconnection capacity increases from 43.5 TVA km to 69.6 TVA km. The newly added interconnection routes reduces the congestion in the existing line capacity with an exception to the Vietnam-Laos and Thailand-Malay Peninsula-Singapore interconnection chain. Further expansion to incorporate the IRENA network topology enhances the total interconnection capacity to 86.3 TVA km.

IRENA's network topology reduces annual system costs by €322.9 billion to €318.9 billion, only a €4 billion savings from the original total system cost as shown in Table 4.1. While the financial savings from grid integration are modest, the increased share of renewables and reduced emissions make it a promising path for decarbonization.

Fig. 4.3.: PyPSA-SEA under BAU and IRENA network topology in 2050

Parameter	(Unit)	Category	EXIST	AIMS	IRENA
Transmission Capacity	(TVA km)	Internal	344.9	335.5	346.2
		Regional	43.5	69.6	86.3
Transmission Cost	(Bill €/a)	Internal	14.9	14.5	15.4
		Regional	1.9	4.0	5.4
		Total	16.8	18.4	20.8
Added Cost vs. EXIST			-	1.6	4.0
Annualized System Cost			322.9	319.1	318.9
Net Savings vs. EXIST	(Bill €/a)		-	3.8	4.0

Tab. 4.1.: PyPSA-SEA under BAU transmission capacity and cost and its impact on annualized system cost

4.2.2 Decarbonization Policy Targets

Fig. 4.4.: PyPSA-SEA with under DEC targets and existing network topology **Top Left:** Capacity development **Top Right:** Electricity development **Bottom:** Time series of the year 2050 between 01.05 and 07.05

As mentioned in the Methodologies Chapter 3.4, there are three decarbonization policy targets, Business-as-Usual (BAU) where there is no emission constraints, Stable Emissions (SE) where the total annual emission in 2050 is equivalent to that of 2020, and Deep Decarbonization (DEC) where the total annual emission in 2050 is one tenth to that of 2020.

In contrast to models under BAU with different network topologies, models under DEC show significant changes in capacity and cost. By 2050, the total capacity is projected to be 2373 GW or 1.8 times greater than the baseline pathway, ensuring that more than 90% percent of the total energy produced comes from renewable sources. Figure 4.4 shows the capacity and energy production development when the emissions of 2050 is limited to 10% of 2020.

The time series shown in Figure 4.4 illustrates the model's hourly performance. Solar generation significantly surpasses the region's electricity demand, with the excess energy being stored in batteries. Wind energy generation is particularly valuable when solar power is unavailable, and offshore wind provides a consistent source of renewable energy.

The distribution of renewable power plants is shown in Figure 4.5. Significant capacities of solar PV are dispatched in mainland Southeast Asia, while onshore wind is primarily deployed near coastal areas. Notably, there is a high concentration of offshore wind capacities in the Java-Bali subregion, indicating that land-based renewable resources are fully saturated, requiring a shift to offshore sources.

The dispatch of offshore wind capacities significantly affects the marginal cost of electricity in the Java-Bali subregion specifically, and the overall system cost more broadly. Under the baseline scenario, the marginal price of electricity in Java-Bali is projected to be 56 €/MWh in 2050. Under DEC targets, it is expected to be 436 €/MWh. For the entire system, this results in an estimated total system cost of €646 billion €/a by 2050, which is two times higher than the baseline scenario.

Conversely, this approach effectively reduces the reliance on coal-fired power plants, with their energy generation nearly nonexistent by 2040. Due to stringent emission constraints, the model utilizes its CO₂ emission stock more efficiently by transitioning from coal to gas, and eventually phasing out gas as well in 2050.

In conclusion, extending grid interconnections alone does not lead to complete decarbonization. However, stringent decarbonization policy targets can achieve decarbonization, but at a high economic and social cost. To optimize decarbonization pathways, both actions must be undertaken simultaneously, coupling ambitious decarbonization policy targets with interregional grid integration.

Fig. 4.5.: PyPSA-SEA with 2050 electricity demand under DEC target and existing network topology

In the next section, we explore the relationship between different network topologies under the same DEC targets.

4.3 ASEAN Power Grid Analysis

In this section, we explore cost-optimal pathways for energy system development, focusing on the grid interconnections named the ASEAN Power Grid proposed by AIMS and IRENA to meet Deep Decarbonization Policy (DEC) targets. We begin by examining how these interconnections affect the utilization of regional renewable energy potential and the resulting marginal electricity prices. Next, we outline the total system costs, including transmission expenses. Lastly, we assess the infrastructure and operational requirements for each country and subregion to implement these modeled scenarios.

Southeast Asia boasts significant renewable energy potential, but the affordability and availability of these resources vary across the region. To illustrate this, we present Figure 4.6, where the y-axis displays the LCOE for each renewable energy source, and the size of each dot indicates the corresponding renewable energy potential.

Fig. 4.6.: Energy generation weighted LCOE for various renewable energy sources, with size representing their availability. Technology cost of the year 2050 and weather data of 2018

According to Figure 4.6, solar energy has the lowest LCOE across all regions. Onshore wind is competitive in certain areas, such as Vietnam and the Philippines. Their energy potential is comparable to the projected electricity demand for 2050. Given the extensive marine areas in all countries and subregions, except Laos, offshore wind holds the highest renewable potential. However, it is generally the most expensive renewable energy option.

Unlike fossil-fuel power plants, the distribution of renewable energy resources does not align with regional electricity demand. Solar energy is typically the first to be exhausted before other renewable resources are utilized. Without extending grid interconnections to new regions, this leads to the situation depicted in Figure 4.7.

Fig. 4.7.: Energy generation distribution with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and existing network topology

Figure 4.7 illustrates the distribution of energy generation and consumption. It is evident from this figure that some countries and subregions generate more or less electricity than they consume, while others produce just enough to meet their own needs. This distinction highlights which countries and subregions are capable of trading electricity and which have isolated grids.

Thailand, Laos, and Cambodia have a surplus of renewable energy, allowing them to export electricity to regions where renewable energy is less affordable. This advantage is not present in isolated grid networks. While some countries have an ample supply of affordable renewable energy to meet their demands, others must rely on more expensive renewable resources. The impact of this situation is illustrated through the marginal price in Figure 4.8.

Interconnected countries and subregions tend to have synchronized marginal prices. Isolated networks may benefit from lower average marginal prices, as seen in Myanmar, Sarawak, Kalimantan, and Nusa Tenggara. However, regions such as Sabah, Brunei, Sumatra, Papua, and Java-Bali have high marginal prices up by a factor of 3. Additionally, it is crucial to analyze the marginal price not only by averages but also by median and maximum values, as these figures will vary with different network topologies.

Fig. 4.8.: Electricity marginal price with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and existing network topology. The red annotation is the maximum marginal price that is above 1000€/MWh

If proposed interconnection plans are implemented, energy generation will shift from regions with less cost-effective renewable sources to renewable hotspots. These hotspots can produce energy without being limited by their own electricity demand, as illustrated in Figure 4.9.

The key difference between Figure 4.7, which utilizes only the existing network topology, and Figure 4.9 is that Myanmar and the Philippines can now export their inexpensive renewable electricity. Additionally, subregions such as Sumatra and Java-Bali can reduce their energy production and import cheaper electricity, which is supported using the Figure 4.10.

The most significant effect of the interconnection is the reduction of the average marginal price in all connected regions to below 100 €/MWh. The regions that remain isolated are Nusa-Tenggara, Sulawesi, Maluku, and West Papua. Additionally, the maximum marginal price in the integrated networks is approximately 400 €/MWh, indicating that the network provides price stabilization benefits.

This trend is also reflected in IRENA's modeled interconnection plans as shown in the Appendix Figure A.2. By incorporating Sulawesi and Nusa-Tenggara into the ASEAN power grid, more renewable resources from these regions are utilized and exported to Java-Bali. While this does not significantly impact the average marginal price, it

Fig. 4.9.: Energy generation distribution with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and AIMS network topology

Fig. 4.10.: Electricity marginal price with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and AIMS network topology. The red annotation is the maximum marginal price that is above 1000€/MWh

further reduces the maximum marginal price to below 800 €/MWh, hence enhancing grid stability to the whole interconnected regions.

Fig. 4.11.: PyPSA-SEA with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and AIMS network topology **Top Left:** Capacity development **Top Right:** Electricity development **Bottom:** Time series of the year 2050 between 01.05 and 07.05

Parameter	(Unit)	Category	EXIST	AIMS	IRENA
Transmission Capacity	(TVA km)	Internal	649.8	1127.2	990.7
		Regional	85.6	252.2	256.3
Transmission Cost	(Bill €/a)	Internal	27.7	47.8	42.9
		Regional	3.7	15.9	18.0
		Total	31.4	63.8	60.9
Added Cost vs. EXIST			-	32.4	29.5
Annualized System Cost	(Bill €/a)		646.2	385.3	374.0
Net Savings vs. EXIST			-	-260.9	-272.2

Tab. 4.2.: PyPSA-SEA under DEC targets transmission capacity and cost and its impact on annualized system cost in the year 2050

When looking at the energy system as a whole, one major advantage of expanding interconnections across the region is that it decreases the renewable capacity requirement by approximately 677 GW, while achieving the same renewable energy share of 90%. Both AIMS and IRENA network topologies yield similar results on a macro scale.

This affected the overall system cost of the grid. Offshore wind is typically the most expensive renewable resource, as mentioned in the LCOE Figure 4.6. Replacing offshore wind with solar PV and onshore wind lowers the total system cost, as shown in the center right Figure 4.11.

The AIMS network topology demonstrates a greater daily proportion of energy storage and dispatch, as depicted in the bottom Figure 4.11. This is attributed to the increased utilization of solar PV and reduced reliance on wind. Additionally, it requires 6.36 TWh or 46% less battery storage capacity compared to the existing network topology. When looked in context, grid integration increases the efficiency of battery infrastructure.

The net-benefits of utilizing the most affordable sources of renewable energy to the region with the highest capacity factor outweighs the cost of adding those interregional transmission capacity, as shown in Table 4.2. Transitioning from the existing network topology to the AIMS proposed network topology results in annualized system cost savings of 261 billion €/a, and this savings can be unlocked by investing in 32.3 billion €/a of additional grid extension.

This supports the idea that greater regional interconnectivity reduces overall system costs. Additionally, IRENA network topology achieved further efficiency gains by strategically bypassing already interconnected countries using HVDC lines, which are more cost-effective to expand than upgrading the internal grids of the bypassed regions. This is how the IRENA network topology spends less on transmission cost (29.5 billion €/a) and yet achieve higher net savings of 272 billion €/a compared to AIMS.

Fig. 4.12.: Electricity export and import in 2050 under DEC targets and AIMS network topology

While extending interconnections brings collective benefits to the entire region, these advantages are not evenly distributed. Depending on their unique circumstances and objectives, the specific challenges of grid integration for each country or subregion may outweigh their individual benefits. Consequently, each country and subregion falls into at least one of four categories:

- **Exporter:** Produces more electricity than it consumes. Earn revenue from renewable exports. Requires high investment on renewable capacities and grid infrastructure.
- **Importer:** Consumes more electricity than it produces. Buys renewable energy from neighbours.
- **Intermediary:** The majority of the electricity that is imported is re-exported. Requires high investment on grid infrastructure.
- **Independent:** Disconnected from the ASEAN power grid.

To determine the categories of each country and subregion, Figure 4.13 illustrates the total electricity exports and imports in relation to their internal demand. In the time series of a year, any electricity entering its network from external sources is considered an import, while any electricity leaving the network is regarded as an export. If a country

or a subregion exports the same amount of electricity as it imports in a given year, it may indicate that the country is using neighboring energy supplies to stabilize its grid or to facilitate energy transport to another neighboring country. This relationship is depicted by the diagonal line of Figure 4.13.

Fig. 4.13.: Electricity export and import relative to 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and AIMS network topology

Countries and subregions located above the diagonal line are net importers of electricity, while those below it are net exporters. Java-Bali and Vietnam are clear examples of net importers, whereas the Philippines is a net exporter. If a region’s exports or imports surpass its internal electricity demand, it crosses either the vertical or horizontal lines respectively. This is true for Singapore, where total energy imports exceed internal demand, and for Myanmar, where electricity exports an amount equivalent to 462% of its own demand.

The diagonal gradient area indicates that these countries and subregions act as energy intermediaries. As intermediaries, they can both add and subtract energy in the process. For example, Sarawak imports 106% of its own demand, consumes some, and re-exports an amount equivalent to 90% of its own demand. Conversely, Thailand imports 106% of its own demand, produces a surplus of energy, and re-exports an amount equivalent to 179% of its own demand.

This relationship can reach extreme levels. Sabah transfers an amount equivalent to 479% of its own demand. Similarly, Cambodia and Laos export amounts equivalent to 716% and 883% of their own demands, respectively. This necessitates enhancements in grid capacities across the region, as illustrated in Figure 4.14.

Fig. 4.14.: Transmission grid capacity under DEC targets and AIMS network topology

The transmission grid capacity expansion varies across different countries and subregions. It's important to note that if a country or subregion is represented as a single node or multiple independent nodes, its grid capacity cannot be determined unless it has interconnections with its neighbor. In the AIMS network topology shown in Figure 4.14, this applies to three subregions. Considering this, Thailand has the largest internal grid capacity due to its proximity to major electricity exporters (Myanmar, Laos, Cambodia) and importers (the Malay Peninsula). This places a significant burden on Thailand and its neighbors, which can be alleviated by diversifying the regions connected to the ASEAN power grid.

By adopting the IRENA network topology, Thailand's grid capacity requirement reduced from 495.1 TVA km to 405.5 TVA km, as shown in Figure 4.15. Some of this grid capacity is redistributed to the broader region but as a whole this results in an overall reduction of transmission grid capacity requirement from 1379.4 TVA km to 1247 TVA km. Enhancing interconnections not only reduces the total capacity needed but also balances the capacity requirements across the region. Additionally, The IRENA network

topology generally reduces export-import dependency, except for Sulawesi and Nusa Tenggara.

The transmission grid capacity under the existing network topology is shown in the Appendix Figure A.3.

Fig. 4.15.: Transmission grid capacity under DEC targets and IRENA network topology

4.4 Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down Strategies

Fig. 4.16.: PyPSA-SEA fossil fuel emissions and electricity development in AIMS network topology under **Top:** Business as Usual (BAU) **Center:** Stable Emission (SE) **Bottom:** Deep Decarbonization (DEC)

The following analysis examines the role of coal-fired power plants in a decarbonizing energy system. We begin by analyzing cumulative CO₂ emissions trends from fossil fuel power plants and the energy produced under various decarbonization policy targets. Next, we categorize coal-fired power plants by location and combustion technology to assess their utilization across different scenarios. Based on these findings, we propose a specific phase-out or phase-down policies for each type of coal-fired power plant and for each country and subregion.

From a high-level perspective, the impact is straightforward: the influence of coal-fired power plants on the overall electricity share and carbon emissions decreases as the model projects further into a decarbonized future, as illustrated in Figure 4.16.

Despite generating minimal energy, their capacity is still accounted for in the model. This is because all models up to now include existing and planned coal-fired power plants so long as it is still within its operating lifetime. Consequently, this has led to a decrease in the capacity factor.

As a result, the reduced capacity factor changes the role of coal-fired power plants from their traditional use as baseload energy sources to more flexible power plants. However, the technical aspects of coal technology are not well-suited for this new role. Therefore, if the technology cannot support this, these coal plants will have to be phased out.

From 2020 to 2050, the baseline pathway has in its peak a total of 149 coal-fired power plants across the region, with a combined capacity of 112 GW. This capacity is divided among four different coal technologies, including power plants that specifically burn lignite. The main question are which coal-fired power plant to be decommissioned and when.

To answer this question, a series of heuristic assumptions are made:

- Coal-fired power plants are grouped by their technology type and the country or subregion they are located in.
- Groups of coal-fired power plants with a capacity factor above 40% are allowed to continue operating as they are.
- Groups of coal-fired power plants with a capacity factor below 40% will have their capacity reduced (phased-down) through the decommissioning of some power plants until their aggregate capacity factor exceeds 40%. This reduction is not applied if:
 - The capacity factor in subsequent years is above 40%. In this case, the power plants initially intended for decommissioning are instead mothballed.
 - The capacity required for coal-fired power plants in subsequent years is higher than the current year. The capacity gap is mothballed for future use.

- Groups of coal-fired power plants with a capacity factor below 20% are immediately decommissioned and phased-out. This decommissioning is not applied if:
 - The capacity factor in subsequent years is above 40%. In this case, the entire power plants are mothballed instead of being phased out.
 - The capacity factor in subsequent years is above 20% but below 40%. In this case, the capacity is reduced (phased down) through the decommissioning of some power plants until it meets the requirements of the later years. The remaining capacity is then mothballed.

These heuristic assumptions are integrated into the models for stable emission decarbonization policy targets and AIMS network topology, as illustrated in Figure 4.17. The heatmap on the left displays the aggregated capacity factor for each coal technology across different countries and subregions, while the heatmap on the right represents the power plant operation policies derived from the aforementioned data.

When comparing different coal technologies, it is evident that coal-fired power plants with the lowest efficiency should be phased out first. The term “coal” refers to coal-fired power plants with unknown technology, which are assumed to have an efficiency of 33% according to PyPSA technology data. In this scenario, most of these plants are phased out by 2035. Power plants with subcritical combustion technology, which have the same efficiency as circulating fluidized bed technology (38%), are suitable for phase-down and phase-out by 2045. Coal-fired power plants utilizing the highly efficient supercritical and ultra-supercritical combustion technologies are neither phased-out or phased-down under the Stable Emission decarbonization policy targets.

When comparing different regions, mainland Southeast Asian countries are generally better positioned for an earlier phase-down of low-efficiency coal-fired power plants. This is due to several factors: the availability of competitive renewable energy sources such as hydropower and onshore wind, enhanced grid interconnection options, and relatively low electricity demand in the early years, which leads to an overcapacity of coal-fired power plants. High-efficiency power plants and lignite are sufficient to meet the region’s needs. In contrast, Malaysia and Indonesia rely more heavily on coal-fired power plants due to a lower supply of affordable renewable sources relative to their electricity demand and the challenges posed by their archipelagic geography.

Under the DEC targets, the timeline for the coal phase-down and phase-out has been significantly shortened, as illustrated in Figure 4.18. All characteristics from the previous Figure 4.17 are advanced by five years. Even highly efficient coal-fired power plants are subject to the phase-down and phase-out. Theoretically, the entire coal fleet could be phased out by 2040, with minor exceptions for supercritical and ultra-supercritical power plants in Java-Bali.

Fig. 4.17.: Capacity factor and power plant operation policy under SE targets and AIMS network topology

Fig. 4.18.: Capacity factor and power plant operation policy under DEC targets and AIMS network topology

Coal-fired power plants using lignite as fuel experience a dramatic shift in capacity usage. Before 2030, their capacity factors are consistently above 71.4% across the region, even reaching 100% utilization in 2020 and 2025. However, from 2040 onwards, their capacity factors drop below 3%. This supports the notion that lignite should have a strict phase-out date. These are the necessary steps to reduce emissions to below 10% compared to 2020 levels.

Influence from the ASEAN Power Grid

The final analysis of this section focuses on coal phase-out and phase-down strategies in different network topologies, namely the IRENA and existing network topologies.

When the network topology is expanded to include Nusa-Tenggara and Sulawesi such as in IRENA, a greater number of their coal-fired power plants are utilized compared to the AIMS network topology. Under the SE policy targets, the regional capacity factor in 2050 increases from 25% to 31% from AIMS to IRENA network topology respectively. The more extensive the network connections of a power plant, the broader the region it can dispatch its energy.

This is also evident in the model with only existing network topologies. In this scenario, only Cambodia, Laos, Singapore, Thailand, the Malay Peninsula, and Vietnam are interconnected. Consequently, the remaining countries and subregions experience reduced utilization of their coal-fired power plants, leading to earlier phased-out. When compared to the AIMS network topology under SE policy targets as shown in Figure 4.17, Figure 4.19 demonstrates that subcritical and CFB power plants are phased out earlier. Even supercritical and ultra-supercritical power plants have a defined end date.

Two factors contribute to this effect. The first is the overcapacity of coal-fired power plants relative to electricity demand. However, this has minimal impact on the coal capacity factor under the BAU policy, as existing network topologies show slightly higher coal utilization of 81.3% compared to 80.6%. This leads to the second factor, namely that given the same carbon budget, it is more carbon-efficient to use gas instead of coal in high-load yet isolated regions. Under SE policy targets and only existing network topologies, the regional coal capacity factor decreases to 7% by 2050.

In conclusion and somewhat counterintuitively, grid integration under ambitious decarbonization policy targets prolongs the use of coal-fired power plants. Conversely, achieving ambitious decarbonization policy targets without grid integration requires earlier phase-out of coal-fired power plants.

Fig. 4.19.: Capacity factor and power plant operation policy under SE targets and existing network topology

4.5 Results Summary

KPI by the year 2050	Policy	EXIST	AIMS	IRENA
Renewable Share [%]	BAU	60.2	63.8	65.7
	SE	70.4	74.1	75.6
	DEC	90.8	90.5	90.6
Annual Emission [MtCO ₂ /a]	BAU	1074.7	995.3	956.6
	SE	505.4	505.4	505.4
	DEC	50.5	50.5	50.5
Emission Intensity [gCO ₂ /kWh]	BAU	167.6	155.2	149.2
	SE	78.8	78.8	78.8
	DEC	7.9	7.9	7.9
Coal Capacity Factor [%]	BAU	81.3	80.6	80.6
	SE	6.9	25.3	30.8
	DEC	0	1.8	1.8
Transmission Capacity [TVA km]	BAU	388.5	405.4	432.5
	SE	523.8	640.6	646.4
	DEC	735.3	1379.4	1247
Energy Trade [TWh]	BAU	700.9	1344.8	1537.8
	SE	1352.7	2528.6	2622.5
	DEC	1541.2	5541.3	4854.4
Marginal Price [EUR/MWh]	BAU	50.3	49.8	49.7
	SE	53.4	51.8	51.5
	DEC	100.8	60.1	58.3
Annual System Cost [EUR Bil/a]	BAU	322.9	319.1	318.9
	SE	342.2	332.3	330.3
	DEC	646.2	385.3	374

Tab. 4.3.: PyPSA-SEA Key-Performance-Indicator (KPI) for all decarbonization policy targets and network topologies by the year 2050

A summary of the key findings is presented in Table 4.3. The main points for each section are as follows:

Baseline Pathway

- The baseline pathway assumes no new interregional interconnections and no emissions constraints, i.e Business as Usual (BAU).
- By 2050, the energy system primarily consists of solar PV, battery storage, and gas-fired power plants with renewable energy's share in the overall energy mix rises to 60% from current levels.

- All baseload plants, including coal-fired power plants, remain fully operational under the baseline pathway.
- The annualized system cost under this scenario is €322.9 billion per year.

Decarbonization Pathways

- Extending the interregional interconnections in SEA indeed increases the use and the effectiveness of using renewable energies, while at the same time reduces the system cost.
- Increasing the ambition of the decarbonization policy targets to Deep Decarbonization (DEC) increases the use of renewable energy significantly but with a doubling cost of the energy system compared to the baseline pathway.

ASEAN Power Grid

- The ASEAN Power Grid aims to integrate the transmission lines across all Southeast Asian countries, creating a unified network.
- Grid integration boost energy trade reduces and stabilize the electricity cost in most region. The transmission capacity requirement increases but can be reduced through having connection that bypass certain region.
- Each country and subregion must carefully weigh the impacts of expanding transmission infrastructure and the dependencies on energy supply and demand from neighboring regions.
- The ASEAN Power Grid is essential for decarbonizing the region at a reduced annual system cost from 646 to 385 billion €/a for AIMS network topology and 374 billion €/a for IRENA network topology.

Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down Strategies

- Between 2020 and 2050, the baseline pathway has in its peak a total of 149 coal-fired power plants across the region, with a combined capacity of 112 GW. A phase-out/phase-down strategies is created by investigating the implication of ambitious decarbonization policy targets such as Stable Emission (SE) and Deep Decarbonization (DEC) to the utilization of coal-fired power plants.
- The analysis identifies a clear priority for phase-out, with the least efficient plants retiring first, while the more efficient plants remain longer. However, lignite-fired plants—though inefficient—are retained longer due to their low cost.
- Countries and regions with strong renewable alternatives, particularly in mainland Southeast Asia, are prioritized for early coal phase-out compared to areas with limited renewable resources, such as Java-Bali.

- Stricter emission constraints, such as those set by DEC targets, shift the complete coal phase-out timeline from the 2050s to the 2040s, with lignite plants phased out 15 years earlier.

Within the Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down analysis, the impact of the ASEAN Power grid are also discussed.

- The more extensive the network connections of a power plant, the broader the region it can dispatch its energy. Conversely, the smaller the network connections of a power plant leads to potential overcapacity.
- The decarbonization policy targets significantly influence the carbon budget allocated to fossil-fuel power plants. With the same carbon budget, using gas is more carbon-efficient than coal in high-load, isolated regions.
- Grid integration under ambitious decarbonization policy targets increases the utility of coal-fired plants in newly connected regions, slightly delaying their phase-out.

Validation and Discussion

Ensuring the reliability of PyPSA-SEA results requires thorough validation of the ASEAN Power Grid and analyses of coal phase-out/phase-down scenarios. Validation entails comparing the model's optimization with actual data to verify its accuracy and dependability. Furthermore, discrepancies between the energy models and well-cited literature can give insights and gaps that the model may not have addressed.

Given that the only available historical data for this thesis is from 2020, the validation through comparison of historical data will primarily be on that year. For subsequent years, the comparison of decarbonization pathways and the ASEAN Power Grid will rely on the IRENA Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN and the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook. Additionally, a methodological comparison are conducted on approaches to prioritizing the phase-out of coal-fired power plants, referencing literature mainly from IESR's Financing Indonesia's Coal Phase-Out.

The sensitivity analysis will concentrate on two key areas: the influence of varying weather years on the distribution of renewable energy and its subsequent effects on the ASEAN Power Grid, as well as the implications of stagnant technological development on the coal phase-out/phase-down strategy.

5.1 Comparison from Historical Data

To validate the model for 2020, we use the PyPSA-SEA model with the existing network topology. Decarbonization policy targets are not relevant for this year due to the absence of emission constraints. For historical datasets, we rely on EMBER Electricity Data Explorer data, which includes power plant capacity, annual electricity demand, and generation. Except for annual electricity demand, the data is disaggregated by countries and technology [EMB24].

The model's electricity demand assumptions are derived from historical data provided by EMBER. Conversely, its power plant capacities are established through a combination of powerplantmatching's compiled power plant data and the model's lowest-cost optimization results.

Fig. 5.1.: Comparison between PyPSA model on the year 2020 and historical data. Technologies are as defined by EMBER [@EMB24]

In 2020, electricity production showed notable discrepancies, particularly between gas-fired power plants and hydropower. Gas-fired plants were underutilized, while hydropower was dispatched more than usual. Additionally, the models indicated that Laos and Vietnam produced more electricity than reality, whereas Singapore and Thailand produced less.

There are two main reasons for these discrepancies. First, the PyPSA-SEA model integrates the internal grids of all countries, facilitating the export of hydropower from Laos and Vietnam to Thailand. Second, there are no capacity constraints on electricity trading between countries, allowing Singapore to rely almost entirely on electricity from Malaysia. These limitations are mentioned in the Methodology Chapter 3.5.

Nonetheless, the power plant capacity in PyPSA-SEA slightly surpasses that of the historical data. For fossil fuel power plants, the capacities are sourced from GEM, while the renewable capacities for the year 2020 are obtained from IRENA. Since these capacities are already included, the results remain proportional with actual conditions. Only renewables such as solar PV and wind are able to extend its capacity.

In conclusion, the baseline model for the year 2020 is valid. The discrepancies, such as the surplus of hydropower and the underutilization of gas, are to be expected given the model's limitations.

5.2 Comparison from Literature

As the model develops beyond the year 2020, there is no historical data to validate its accuracy. However, it is possible to compare the results of PyPSA-SEA with those of the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook (AEO8) and IRENA ASEAN Renewable Energy Outlook models. It's important to note that the primary driver for the energy transition, the emission constraints, differs between these models. Additionally, the technology costs vary, and both the AEO8 and IRENA models are sector-coupled, whereas PyPSA-SEA is not currently developed in that manner.

With that as a discretion in mind, and the fact that there are many options of data points to compare, the model comparison will only focus on the most ambitious pathway of each outlook, namely the Carbon Neutrality Scenario (CNS) from the AEO8 and 1.5-Scenario with 90% renewable power generation (1.5-S RE90) from the IRENA ASEAN Renewable Energy Outlook. For the former, it is compared to the model run with AIMS network topology, while the latter with IRENA network topology.

5.2.1 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook

The Carbon Neutrality Scenario (CNS) presents a strategy for ASEAN to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2050, focusing on cost-effective optimization. This approach utilizes various renewable resources and employs carbon capture and storage (CCS) for fossil fuel power plants, alongside bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). All

fossil fuel power plants that do not implement CCS will be decommissioned. For analysis, two key data points from the CNS are available: capacity development and power generation from 2025 to 2050 [SY24]. To ensure a fair comparison, we developed a custom PyPSA-SEA model distinct from the one used in the results section. This version aligns with the total electricity demand of the CNS and aggregates technologies in the figure to match those specified in the CNS configuration.

According to the capacity development in Figures 5.2 and 5.3, it is evident that the CNS employs fewer capacities than the PyPSA-SEA model under both Business-as-Usual and Deep Decarbonization policy scenarios. Additionally, CNS showcases a more diversified technology mix, featuring a greater share of wind, geothermal, tidal, wave, biomass, and nuclear energy. The capacity of coal-fired power plants remains stable, while gas-fired power plants see an increase in capacity, accompanied by a reduction in energy output.

Fig. 5.2.: Capacity and electricity development for PyPSA-SEA **Top:** under BAU **Bottom:** DEC targets. The components are based on the 8th AEO classification. Nuclear power, tidal and wave are not modeled in PyPSA-SEA.

Fig. 5.3.: Capacity and electricity development for the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook (AEO) CNS [A@SY24]. All use AIMS network topology. The components are based on the 8th AEO classification. Nuclear power, tidal and wave are not modeled in PyPSA-SEA.

In the PyPSA-SEA model, the share of solar energy in the mix for the year 2050 varies between 60% and 77%. In contrast, solar contributes only 24% to the CNS energy mix, while wind power surpasses solar at 30%, with geothermal following in third place at 10%.

The 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook does not provide detailed information on the interconnection capacity needed to achieve the CNS results. However, it does include existing and proposed transmission capacity projects based on the 2022 AIMS report. Table 5.1 summarizes the interconnection capacities from both the AIMS report and PyPSA-SEA results. The Power Development Plan (PDP) serves as the base scenario, incorporating official interconnection proposals currently under discussion [ACA24].

To compare the interconnection capacity between the AIMS report and PyPSA-SEA, an accurate alignment of base years is essential. However, this alignment is challenging for several reasons:

- The AIMS report analyzes specific interconnections individually, whereas the PyPSA-SEA model aggregates total interconnection capacity between countries and subregions.
- In the PyPSA-Earth workflow, low-resolution shapefiles for countries and subregions result in mischaracterization, where some OSM substations and lines are incorrectly assigned to neighboring countries.

Model Year Value	Exist 2022 GW	PDP 2040 GW	Base 2020 GW	BAU 2040 GW	DEC 2040 GW
Laos - Myanmar	-	0.35	0.06	0.05	0.05
Vietnam - Laos	1.108	1.158	5.44	6.8	3.64
Thailand - Laos	6.127	6.772	16.8	18.5	17.87
Thailand - Myanmar	-	1.25	1.89	1.72	1.69
Cambodia - Laos	0.2	0.50	2.2	2.61	4.08
Cambodia - Thailand	0.23	1.00	1.54	11.5	19.02
Cambodia - Vietnam	0.2	0.25	3.27	15.3	24.56
Sabah (M) - Philippines	-	0.20	3.91	4.82	4.82
Malay Peninsular (M) - Thailand	0.3	0.35	6.08	6.98	10.97
Sarawak (M) - Brunei	-	0.1	0.75	1.15	0.75
Sarawak (M) - Malay Peninsular (M)	-	-*	3.08	4.82	4.82
Sarawak (M) - Sabah (M)	0.05	0.15	0.56	6.15	4.37
Singapore - Malay Peninsular (M)	0.525	1.05	6.91	6.73	6.96
Kalimantan (I) - Sabah (M)	-	0.20	0.03	1.44	1.11
Kalimantan (I) - Sarawak (M)	0.23	0.83	0.25	1.14	0.95
Sumatra (I) - Malay Peninsular (M)	-	2.00	3.05	4.82	4.82
Sumatra (I) - Singapore	-	1.20	0.36	2.36	1.93
Java-Bali (I) - Kalimantan (I)	-	-*	0.35	4.76	4.79
Java-Bali (I) - Sumatra (I)	-	6.20	2.74	4.82	4.82
Total	7.70	23.56	59.27	106.47	122.02
Increase from Exist/Base Year	-	15.86	-	47.20	62.75

Tab. 5.1.: Comparison between the interconnection capacity in AIMS report and the maximum interconnection capacity utilized in PyPSA-SEA results. * indicates that the PDP results do not require interconnections, even though the option is available [ACA24]

- In PyPSA-Earth construction of the base network, all lines and links are standardized to a given capacity. All HVDC links for example are standardized to a voltage of 500 kV, giving them a default capacity of 4.82 GW.

This problem not only occurs in this custom PyPSA-SEA model for CNS, but also to all of the models in the result section. To address this, the values from PyPSA-SEA in Table 5.1 represent the maximum electricity capacity that flows within that year, rather than the model's actual capacity results which depends its initial capacity.

There is a significant discrepancy between Table 5.1 and the actual capacity results from PyPSA-SEA, as shown in Appendix Table B.1. This mismatch can result in a take-or-pay scenario within the model, where the initial interconnection costs must be paid regardless of whether the interconnections are fully utilized. Notably, seven out of the 19 interconnections listed in Appendix Table B.1 have maximum capacity flows lower than their initial capacity. Addressing this limitation will be essential in future work.

Despite these limitations, several insights can be taken. Firstly, to meet the PDP, a capacity expansion of 15.86 GW by 2040 is required—triple the current capacity. Achieving this in the Business-as-Usual scenario would require expansions of 47.2 GW. Additionally, meeting the Deep Decarbonization Policy Target would require expansions of 62.75 GW. This raises feasibility questions, as discussed in Chapter 4.3 on grid expansion, about deploying such a substantial volume of transmission capacity.

On the other hand, the AIMS report recommends updating the PDP every 3-5 years to align with the power development ambitions of each ASEAN member state. As member states integrate the ASEAN Power Grid based on the PDP, additional low-hanging interconnection opportunities can be identified, paving the way for further expansion proposals. This process is iterative and relies on coordinated efforts among all stakeholders.

5.2.2 IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN

While the ASEAN Energy Outlook provide insights into the various types of technology that could be implemented, the IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN provide insight on the distribution of these technologies in the region. Figure 5.4 compares the power generation between PyPSA-SEA main results and IRENA's 1.5 Scenario with 90% renewable power generation (1.5-S RE90) for the year 2050. Both of them uses the same IRENA's network topology and IRENA's electricity demand assumption for this scenario [Adi+22].

The imbalance between power generation and electricity demand of a region in PyPSA-SEA tends to increase with higher levels of decarbonization as shown in the top three Figure 5.4. However, the 1.5-S RE90 model argues otherwise, showing a smaller gap due to the use of renewable energy sources with outputs independent from the weather such as geothermal and biomass, along with abated gas-fired power plants. Figure 5.4 lacks details on the disaggregated power generation across subregions in Indonesia and Malaysia. According to IRENA, which coincides with the PyPSA-SEA results, Java-Bali will be the largest energy importer in the region. However, those import are met through the renewable energy generated from other subregions in Indonesia instead of other countries.

Although not explicitly addressed in IRENA's report, there appear to be technological or security constraints that limit electricity exports and imports to levels below those suggested as the lowest-cost solutions in the PyPSA-SEA models.

The key insight from this section is that both the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook and IRENA's ASEAN Renewable Energy Outlook advocate for a diverse energy mix. This includes expanding firm renewable energy sources and utilizing fossil-fuel power plants equipped with carbon capture and storage technologies. This approach partly explains the reduced levels of interregional trade and fewer interconnectors in their models. The feasibility of expanding the transmission line in PyPSA-SEA needs to be assessed.

Fig. 5.4.: Energy generation distribution of **Top:** Stable Emission (SE) **Center:** Deep Decarbonization Emission (DEC) target **Bottom:** IRENA 1.5-S RE90. All with 2050 electricity demand using IRENA network topology

5.2.3 IESR's Financing Indonesia's Coal Phase-Out and ACE Assessment

The 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook and IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN primarily examine the future energy system in Southeast Asia, while the reports from IESR, TransitionZero, Rocky Mountain Institute, the Sierra Club, and Carbon Tracker concentrate more on analyzing coal phase-out strategies. For this section we are focusing only at IESR's Financing Indonesia's Coal Phase-Out report.

The IESR report adopts a three-step approach that combines top-down and bottom-up analysis. First, it establishes a top-down national net-zero transition pathway, similar to those in the IRENA and AEO8 reports. The results are then used to determine phase-out dates for individual coal plants. Finally, a detailed bottom-up cost-benefit analysis is performed for each plant, incorporating social and economic externalities [Cui+22].

There are both similarities and differences between IESR's report and the use of PyPSA-SEA in this thesis. Both approaches utilize energy system optimization models: IESR's report builds on their previous analysis for Indonesia's 2050 decarbonization to model an energy transition pathway, using these results to propose phase-out dates for coal-fired power plants [IES21]. The primary difference is that PyPSA-SEA does not extend to the third phase of the analysis.

As noted in the Introduction, ACE critiques these reports, arguing that they rely too heavily on the LCOE of renewables and underestimate the additional costs associated with extending the grid infrastructure and the loss from curtailment [PS24]. Looking at IESR's report, their research do include variables mentioned by ACE in their top-down analysis. However, these information is difficult to integrate in the bottom-up cost-benefit analysis.

Consider, for instance, grid infrastructure. IESR's energy transition pathway, based on the LUT Energy System Transition Model, acknowledges that achieving the optimal scenario requires interregional connections to deliver electricity to Java-Bali. These grid interconnections contribute more to the total CAPEX in the system cost than most renewable capacities, apart from solar PV [IES21]. The challenge, however, is that we cannot determine what portion of these interconnection costs is specifically attributable to decommissioning any single coal-fired power plant.

A potential solution to address this issue is to use PyPSA's high spatial and temporal resolution to compare system costs between models that include with ones that exclude every single coal-fired power plant one by one. With 149 individual coal-fired power plants, this requires creating at least 149 distinct models. The complexity can increase

further when considering different phase-out years within each plant's operational lifetime. Because of the number of models needed, this approach is not pursued in this thesis.

The current conclusion is that PyPSA-SEA takes a similar approach to IESR's report in developing a coal phase-out or phase-down strategy. However, methods for addressing ACE's criticisms remain untested.

5.3 Sensitivity Analysis

There are two parameters that are analyzed in the model sensitivity analysis section: the impacts of the weather year on the distribution of renewable dispatch, and the impact of stagnant technology development on the coal phase-out/phase-down strategy.

5.3.1 Weather Year

As noted in Chapter 2.1.1 of the PyPSA-SEA dataset, ERA5 provides global climate datasets from 1950 onward [Her+20]. However, the hourly load demand generated through machine learning approaches [Mat+21] in the PyPSA-Earth databundle is only available for the weather years 2011, 2013, and 2018. Therefore, for practical reasons, we limit our focus to these three years.

Using the LCOE graph previously employed in the ASEAN Power Grid analysis, we highlight deviations across at least the three selected weather years for the scenario year 2050. Figure 5.5 illustrates that renewable technologies exhibit differing levels of LCOE and energy potential variability. Offshore wind connected via DC lines demonstrates the highest energy potential in the region; even in its least favorable year, it surpasses the combined energy potential of all other variable renewable energy sources. Additionally, offshore wind shows the smallest LCOE variation among wind technologies. However, solar PV emerges as the technology with the most consistent energy potential and LCOE.

Because of its consistency, solar PV share remains relatively constant across different weather years, as shown in Figure 5.6. In contrast, the electricity generated from onshore and offshore wind turbines fluctuates, with a less prominent offshore wind turbines taking the lead in 2013. This highlights the need for a diverse mix of wind turbine technologies to hedge the impact of different weather conditions.

Fig. 5.5.: Weather year comparison of Energy generation weighted LCOE for various renewable energy sources, with size representing their availability. Technology cost of the year 2050

Fig. 5.6.: Energy generation distribution with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and IRENA network topology with **Top:** 2013, **Bottom:** 2011 weather year

As the distribution of generated energy shifts, interconnection capacity must adjust accordingly as shown in Appendix Table B.2. This variability presents a challenge when

modeling and proposing interregional interconnections, as they may be suboptimal in certain weather years but are designed to be cost-optimal over the long term when considered comprehensively.

The near-optimal feasible range for interconnection capacity lies between the minimum and maximum values of interregional interconnections, with this range potentially broadening if additional years are considered. Conducting an analysis at this level of granularity would require for example stochastic programming or applying the modeling-to-generate-alternatives (MGA) approach as outlined in the works of Neumann, F., and Brown, T. [NB21], which is beyond the scope of this thesis.

5.3.2 Stagnant Technologies

The results for all network topologies and decarbonization policy targets in PyPSA are highly influenced by the development of renewable technologies and the supporting infrastructure. As detailed in the Data Chapter 2, PyPSA-SEA relies on the compiled PyPSA technology data, which is used to calculate the capital and marginal costs. Table 5.2 presents the annualized capital costs of key technologies.

Carrier	Unit	2020	2030	2040	2050
Coal (All types)	€/kW	358.55	358.55	358.55	358.55
Lignite	€/kW	337.21	337.21	337.21	337.21
Combined-Cycle Gas	€/kW	110.92	104.79	102.47	100.16
Offshore Wind (DC)	€/kW	338.78	297.05	281.83	278.18
Offshore Wind (AC)	€/kW	304	262.24	247.4	244.25
Onshore Wind	€/kW	113.58	101.64	95.63	94.13
Solar	€/kW	56.71	39.3	33.03	30.13
Battery Storage	€/kWh	23.17	12.89	8.02	6.4

Tab. 5.2.: Investment cost for generators and battery storage from 2020 to 2050

Table 5.2 shows a substantial reduction in the annualized capital costs for renewable technologies, with wind technologies decreasing by approximately 17-20%, solar PV by 47%, and battery storage capacity by 72%. Given these significant cost reductions shown in Table 5.2, an alternative model was run to assess how the energy system would evolve if technology costs in 2050 remained at 2020 levels.

Figure 5.7 summarizes the baseline pathways of the alternative model. In contrast to the model with developing technologies, this model relies more heavily on gas-fired power plants, which become the largest energy source by 2050. While solar generation remains cheaper than natural gas, gas-fired power plants are still more cost-effective than

combining solar PV with battery storage, resulting in a more limited role for renewable energy overall.

Fig. 5.7.: PyPSA-SEA with 2050 electricity demand under BAU targets using only existing network topology **Top Left:** Capacity development **Top Right:** Electricity development **Bottom:** Time series of the year 2050 between 05-01 and 05-07

In the stagnating technology model, emissions in 2050 are over three times higher than in 2020, contrasting with the developing technology model, where emissions are only double, as shown in Figure 5.8. This indicates that the alternative model would require stricter emission constraints to meet Stable Emission and Deep Decarbonization policy targets. Stricter constraints lead to higher shadow prices for CO₂ emissions, which in turn makes coal-fired power plants less viable, as gas-fired plants utilize the limited CO₂ budget more efficiently.

Figure 5.9 illustrates this clearly, comparing the operational policies of power plants in the developing technology model on the left and the stagnating technology model on the right, both under the same network topology and Stable Emission decarbonization targets. Coal-fired power plants, even highly efficient supercritical and ultra-supercritical units, are phased out by 2045, with lignite-fired plants phased out even earlier due to their higher emissions. Gas-fired power plants reach peak utilization in the late 2040s in this model. These characteristics are also evident when comparing the same model under Deep Decarbonization policy targets, as shown in Figure B.2 in the appendix.

This leads to an interesting and unexpected conclusion: if technological costs, especially for solar and battery storage, progress more slowly than projected by PyPSA's cost predictions, coal-fired power plants will need to be phased-out even more rapidly due to the increased reliance on gas.

Fig. 5.8.: PyPSA-SEA fossil fuel emissions and electricity development under Business As Usual (BAU) with AIMS network topology with **Top:** stagnant technologies **Bottom:** developing technologies

Fig. 5.9.: Capacity factor and power plant operation policy under Stable Emission decarbonization policy targets and AIMS network topology

5.4 Validation Summary

The main point for each section are as follows:

Comparison from Historical Data

- The PyPSA-SEA base model for 2020 closely aligns with actual electricity demand and power plant capacity, as its data is sourced from external historical data.
- However, the model shows an excess of electricity generation from hydropower and a shortfall from gas-fired plants, likely due to the unconstrained electricity trade allowed between countries. This limitation is noted in the model's methodology.

Comparison from Literature

- In the most ambitious scenarios from the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook and IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN, a more diverse energy mix is proposed, including renewable energy sources and fossil-fuel plants with carbon capture and storage (CCS), which are not yet incorporated in PyPSA-SEA.
- IRENA's report indicate technological or security limits on electricity imports and exports, keeping energy trade low compared PyPSA-SEA's models.

Sensitivity Analysis

- Solar energy demonstrates the most stable Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) and potential within the region, according to the weather year analysis.
- Energy generation from onshore and offshore wind turbines varies, with a less prominent wind technology in one year potentially leading in others.
- Renewable capacity and interregional interconnections must be resilient enough to support varying weather conditions.
- In a scenario where 2050 technology costs remain at 2020 levels, the energy mix is dominated by gas-fired power plants, with limited solar expansion and minimal battery usage.
- Without technological advancements, total annual emissions in 2050 would triple compared to 2020, rather than doubling as projected in the baseline pathway.
- With higher costs for renewables and storage, the model leans on gas-fired power plants and phases out coal plants earlier to manage emissions within the available budget.

Conclusion

In this study, we aimed to address questions about the ASEAN power grid and the coal phase-down/phase-out strategy in SEA. By examining three different network topologies and three decarbonization policy targets, we can answer these questions through a case-by-case comparison, with a summary of Key-Performance-Indicators as shown in Table 4.3.

The overall results from PyPSA-SEA suggest that the electricity system can achieve decarbonization while maintaining an electricity marginal price lower than that of the 2020 baseline. This requires two key actions: phasing out coal-fired power plants, beginning with the least efficient and fully retiring all by early 2045, and establishing interregional connections at least to the options proposed by AIMS.

When the analysis of the ASEAN power grid is combined with the coal phase-down/phase-out strategy, some expected and unexpected outcomes emerge. The former being that the ASEAN power grid gains greater relevance as the network becomes more decarbonized, while the latter being that an increase in interregional connections enable greater use of coal-fired power plants while still meeting the same emission targets.

These insights are derived by comparing between PyPSA-SEA models, but these results should be interpreted cautiously through additional sensitivity analysis. Variations in weather years significantly influence the optimal renewable energy mix and interconnection capacity, while changes in technology costs affect not only renewables, but also the roles of gas-fired and coal-fired power plants in a decarbonizing energy system.

Furthermore, PyPSA-SEA has certain limitations compared to the 8th ASEAN Energy Outlook and IRENA's Renewable Energy Outlook for ASEAN. To start, these sources incorporate a broader mix of technologies that are either not included or not easily scalable within the current framework of PyPSA-SEA. These technologies include geothermal, bioenergy, fossil-fuel plants with carbon capture and storage (CCS), nuclear, and tidal energy [Adi+22] [SY24]. Additionally, the level of transmission capacity required between countries and subregions to achieve the outcomes modeled by PyPSA-SEA is considerably higher than current targets. Furthermore, practical constraints on energy trade between countries—whether due to technological limitations or security concerns—are not addressed in PyPSA-SEA.

PyPSA-SEA does not align with individual countries' policy targets. Instead, it models the Southeast Asia region as a unified entity with collective targets, an important limitation in the model as outlined in Methodology section 3.5. As a result, it cannot provide concrete policy recommendations such as those found in the literature. However, the results presented here challenge certain assumptions commonly accepted when models strictly adhere to current policy targets, namely:

- **Sustainable Energy Dependency:** The potential benefits of the ASEAN Power Grid are limited if countries are unwilling to trade electricity at a substantial share of their demand. Both the literature and the insight obtained from PyPSA-SEA emphasize the challenges involved in reaching this goal, such as the need for internal grid expansion and addressing technological and security concerns. However, addressing these challenges can lead to significant energy and system cost savings as shown in PyPSA-SEA.
- **Collective Emission Trading System:** The status and conditions of coal-fired power plants vary across countries and subregions, meaning that some areas should phase out their plants sooner than others for a cost-effective energy transition. Currently, emissions trading in ASEAN operates only at the national level [SY24]. An ASEAN-wide emissions trading system would allow regions such as Mainland SEA with greater access to alternative energy sources to phase-out coal plants earlier, while providing flexibility for coal use in regions such as Java-Bali where the transition is more challenging.

During the course of creating this thesis, PyPSA and PyPSA-Earth are undergoing rapid development for modeling energy transitions. The model code for this thesis was forked from PyPSA-Earth version 0.3.0. By the time of submission, PyPSA-Earth had advanced to version 0.4.1, incorporating features such as sector coupling and myopic foresight. It is hoped that the insights from this thesis will serve as a foundation for future iterations of PyPSA-SEA and contribute to the decarbonization strategies of Southeast Asian countries.

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Appendix Chapter: Results

A.1 Appendix Section: Baseline Pathways

A.2 Appendix Section: Decarbonization Pathways

Fig. A.1.: PyPSA-SEA with 2050 electricity demand under BAU and AIMS network topology

Fig. A.2.: Electricity marginal price with 2050 electricity demand under DEC targets and IRENA network topology. The red annotation is the maximum marginal price that is above 1000€/MWh

Fig. A.3.: Transmission grid capacity under DEC targets and existing network topology

A.3 Appendix Section: ASEAN Power Grid Analysis

A.4 Appendix Section: Coal Phase-Out/Phase-Down Strategies

Fig. A.4.: PyPSA-SEA fossil fuel emissions and energy development under AIMS network topology in SE targets

Appendix Chapter: Validation

Model Year Value	Exist 2022 GW	PDP 2040 GW	Base 2020 GW	BAU 2040 GW	DEC 2040 GW
Laos - Myanmar	-	0.35	0.09	0.07	0.07
Vietnam - Laos	1.108	1.158	7.77	9.72	5.21
Thailand - Laos	6.127	6.772	72.25	74.21	74.09
Thailand - Myanmar	-	1.25	2.70	2.46	2.42
Cambodia - Laos	0.2	0.50	3.15	3.73	5.83
Cambodia - Thailand	0.23	1.00	2.20	16.43	27.17
Cambodia - Vietnam	0.2	0.25	4.67	21.85	35.08
Sabah (M) - Philippines	-	0.20	4.82	4.82	4.82
Malay Peninsular (M) - Thailand	0.3	0.35	6.75	7.41	13.12
Sarawak (M) - Brunei	-	0.1	1.07	1.64	1.07
Sarawak (M) - Malay Peninsular (M)	-	-*	4.82	4.82	4.82
Sarawak (M) - Sabah (M)	0.05	0.15	0.79	8.78	6.24
Singapore - Malay Peninsular (M)	0.525	1.05	9.87	9.61	9.94
Kalimantan (I) - Sabah (M)	-	0.20	0.04	2.05	1.58
Kalimantan (I) - Sarawak (M)	0.23	0.83	8.00	8.00	8.00
Sumatra (I) - Malay Peninsular (M)	-	2.00	4.82	4.82	4.82
Sumatra (I) - Singapore	-	1.20	4.82	4.82	4.82
Java-Bali (I) - Kalimantan (I)	-	-*	4.82	4.82	4.82
Java-Bali (I) - Sumatra (I)	-	6.20	4.82	4.82	4.82
Total	7.70	23.56	148.27	194.88	218.74
Increase from Exist/Base Year	-	15.86	-	46.61	70.47

Tab. B.1.: Interconnection capacity comparison between AIMS report and PyPSA-SEA results.
* indicates that the PDP results do not require interconnections, even though the option is available [ACA24]

B.1 Appendix Section: Sensitivity Analysis

Weather Year Units	2018 TVA km	2013 TVA km	2011 TVA km
Laos - Myanmar	2.1	0.22	1.92
Vietnam - Laos	12.46	17.89	13.73
Vietnam - Myanmar	19.92	12.32	18.09
Thailand - Laos	17.28	20.52	17.53
Thailand - Myanmar	13.33	40.83	22.4
Thailand - Vietnam	8.38	3.01	9.95
Cambodia - Laos	2.6	3.79	2.32
Cambodia - Thailand	10.53	4.92	9.63
Cambodia - Vietnam	12.56	13.99	11.64
Sabah (M) - Philippines	17.38	26.24	18.39
Malay Peninsular (M) - Thailand	32.46	45.6	35.92
Sarawak (M) - Brunei	0.37	0.37	0.37
Sarawak (M) - Malay Peninsular (M)	11.1	21.01	15.02
Sarawak (M) - Sabah (M)	2.55	3.66	2.92
Singapore - Malay Peninsular (M)	1.79	1.84	1.77
Kalimantan (I) - Sabah (M)	5.16	3.57	4.88
Kalimantan (I) - Sarawak (M)	2.27	2.27	2.27
Sumatra (I) - Malay Peninsular (M)	24.91	36.01	27.8
Sumatra (I) - Singapore	0.34	0.34	0.34
Sumatra (I) - Thailand	6.23	3.88	9.2
Sulawesi (I) - Kalimantan (I)	7.41	2.59	6.49
Java-Bali (I) - Kalimantan (I)	6.08	5.1	5.31
Java-Bali (I) - Sumatra (I)	17.65	23.96	20.88
Nusa-Tenggara (I) - Java-Bali (I)	9.94	4.29	9.88
Nusa-Tenggara (I) - Sulawesi (I)	11.52	3.72	13
Total Interregional Capacity	256.32	301.94	281.65

Tab. B.2.: Interregional capacity comparison for PyPSA under DEC targets and IRENA network topology. **Bold** numbers shows the largest capacity for that interconnection

Fig. B.1.: PyPSA-SEA fossil fuel emissions and electricity development under Stable Emission (SE) targets with AIMS network topology with **Top:** stagnant technologies **Bottom:** developing technologies

Fig. B.2.: Capacity factor and power plant operation policy under Deep Decarbonization policy targets and AIMS network topology

Colophon

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Declaration

I hereby declare that I have written this thesis independently without the help of third parties and exclusively using the sources and aids listed. I have marked all passages that are taken from the sources and aids used unchanged or analogously as such. During the preparation of this work the I have used OpenAI's ChatGPT and DeepL Write in order to improve readability and language. I am fully responsible for the selection, adoption and all results of the AI-generated output I used.

I have taken note of the Statutes for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice at TU Berlin dated March 8, 2017 [@Ber24]. I further declare that I have not submitted the thesis in the same or a similar form to any other examination authority.

Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit eigenständig ohne Hilfe Dritter und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Alle Stellen die den benutzten Quellen und Hilfsmitteln unverändert oder sinngemäß entnommen sind, habe ich als solche kenntlich gemacht. Während der Vorbereitung dieser Arbeit habe ich Chat-GPT von OpenAI und DeepL Write verwendet, um die Sprache und Lesbarkeit zu verbessern. Ich verantworte die Auswahl, die Übernahme und sämtliche Ergebnisse des von mir verwendeten KI-generierten Outputs vollumfänglich selbst.

Die Satzung zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis an der TU Berlin vom 8. März 2017 [@Ber24] habe ich zur Kenntnis genommen. Ich erkläre weiterhin, dass ich die Arbeit in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt habe.

Berlin, December 5, 2024

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